

ReNEW

D1.2- Resilience and Sustainability analysis
in IWT and strategic development Baseline
Building Blocks v2

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CEMT	Conférence Européenne des Ministres des Transports
CESNI	European Committee for drawing up standards in the field of inland navigation
CLH	City Logistics Hub
DT	Digital Twin
DoS	Denial of Service
EC	European Commission
ECDIS	Inland Electronic Chart Display Information Service
ENC	Electronic Navigational Charts
ERCC	Emergency Response Coordination Center
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
ISL	Institut für Seeverkehrswirtschaft und Logistik
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
IW	Inland Waterways
IW-NET	Innovation-driven Collaborative European Inland Waterways Transport Network
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LL	Living Lab
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
ReNEW	Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways
RIS	River Information Services
RSQF	Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework
SCRM	Supply Chain Risk Management
SPEI	Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index
SPI	Standardized Precipitation Index
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
VTS	Vessel traffic service
WP	Work Package
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting

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Executive Summary

ReNEW is the acronym for the project "Resilience-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways". This project is funded by the European Commission under the topic "HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-09 "Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways".

A comprehensive hazards and vulnerability scenario catalogue was already developed in the previous version of this deliverable. In this document, this catalogue was used as the basis for a refined analysis of the hazards and threats regarding vulnerabilities and potential consequences, including additional risk analyses for relevant events. This was done based on literature research and surveys of living labs (LL).

The information developed so far in Task 1.1 represents essential key elements for the creation of the Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF). The RSQF is a central component of Task 1.1 and includes various tasks to identify and improve resilience and sustainability in the context of Inland Waterway Transport (IWT). The framework includes several key elements where significant progress has been made in different areas and essential key elements have been provided.

An initial set of strategies for improving resilience and sustainability was formulated, comprising short, medium, and long-term measures. These strategies were derived from literature research, experience from other projects and feedback from LLs.

A comprehensive list of KPIs for sustainability and resilience was already defined and categorized in D1.1. These have already been further refined, categorized, and used by other project partners as input for various deliverables (D1.8, D3.6 and D3.8). Due to the diverse use of these KPIs in different areas of the project and since the KPIs defined in the GA must also be considered, the corresponding planning approaches were formulated to create a meaningful, uniform framework of KPIs together with the project partners.

The general approach for the implementation of CBA was further developed and the future structure outlined. The CBA will be created in the selected scenarios within the LLs, incorporating the proposed measures to improve resilience and sustainability.

Regarding the building blocks which form the basis for the planning, implementation, evaluation and impact assessment of Floating Modular Platforms, autonomous inland vessels, digital twins, and the benchmarking of emission-neutral solutions the list will be continuously updated, expanded, and specified to adapt to evolving project requirements. Several building blocks, data sources, models and libraries were as well collected in other Work Packages and Deliverables. Against this background and since the project transitioned into a phase where practical information utilization became relevant the focus is now more on providing a comprehensive overview to enable project partners the rapid access to the relevant information.

1 Introduction

Inland waterway transportation is considered to play an important role in the decarbonisation and reducing the congestion of the transport sector and consolidating economic development. However, events such as low- or high-water periods can cause potentially long-term disruptions of the respective transport chains.

The main objective of ReNEW is to identify ways to balance the quest towards more sustainability and resilience in inland waterway transportation. As described in the Grant Agreement (GA) this will be carried out by developing decision support tools for strategic planning and operational optimization of inland waterway transport chains, taking resilience and sustainability into account. Innovative solutions fostering the resilience and sustainability of inland waterway infrastructure will be developed and Information Technology (IT) tools such as "green resilient Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) dataspace" and "digital twins" will be implemented in order to enable efficient data exchange between all stakeholders involved.

The ReNEW results are tested and demonstrated in 4 Living Labs:

- Living Lab #1 – Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchromodality City Logistics Hub
- Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management – DIW2024
- Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, in addition, to boosting modal shift
- Living Lab #4 – Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

This document is the fifth deliverable of WP1 – “Methodology for EU Resilient and Sustainable IWT Infrastructure System” and is foreseen as the second contribution for Task 1.1 – “Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks”.

Under WP1, in support of the vision of a resilient and sustainable infrastructure system for inland navigation, a value-based analysis will be undertaken to ensure IWT's adaptation to climate change while maintaining competitiveness. The main aim of WP1 is the development of the ReNEW methodological framework for resilient and sustainable green IWT strategy planning, as well as the establishment of a framework of tools and solutions for analyzing infrastructure interdependencies and safety risks, reconfiguring transportation services, and determining the impact of natural or man-made disasters on the IW ecological environment.

Within Task 1.1 building blocks will be provided that serve as a basis for the planning, operation, and evaluation of new solutions (e.g., autonomous barges), for the digital twins, and for the evaluation and benchmarking of emission-neutral solutions. These building blocks will be tested in the LL scenarios.

Task 1.1. consists of 4 subtasks, which are only outlined below. The detailed description based on the GA can be found in Table 1.

- ST1.1.1 Hazards and vulnerabilities in IW Transport
- ST1.1.2 Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities
- ST1.1.3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs, and metrics.
- ST1.1.4 Resilience and Agility strategies

1.1 Objectives, Deliverable Structure and General Methodology

According to the GA, the description of the deliverable D1.2 Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v2 is the following: “Resilience and Sustainability Models and Simulation Libraries, Data sources 2nd Release, Strategies 1st Release”. This document is the second of three versions, some of the mentioned objectives will be available in their final and fully elaborated version in the last deliverable.

In line with the description of the subtasks of Task 1.1, a primary objective of this deliverable is to conduct a more in-depth analysis of the previously identified, profiled, and catalogued threats and hazards from D1.1. The focus will be on examining event consequences, vulnerabilities, and their pertinence to the ReNEW Living Labs (LL), as detailed in Section 2.

In Section 3 the further steps for the creation of a framework for quantifying resilience and sustainability (RSQF) are described. The objective of this task is to create joint/correlated sustainability and resilience indicators in order to enable their quantification based on the proposed model characteristics, as stated in the Grant Agreement.

The KPIs, as already identified in the previous deliverable, and refined in other deliverables, especially in WP3 - European IWT Data Space and Digital Twin solutions for Resilience and Sustainability will be further refined based on the assessments of the LL according to their relevance and allocated to the general KPIs defined in the GA. The aim is to establish a meaningful set of KPIs and to further refine them in collaboration with project partners. This will be done at a later stage of the project and published in the last deliverable of Task 1.1.

Section 4 will provide additional insights into the preparation of a cost-benefit analysis, explaining the subsequent steps in the process.

The project's initial phase, documented in the previous deliverable version D1.1, and in *D3.8 – Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1* (Resilience and Sustainability Report) and *D3.6 - Green Resilient IWT Digital Twin Generic application v1* (Report on metrics and KPIs for the LL use cases using DT, Data Spaces, and ReNEW services and Solutions Deployed; Simulation Libraries, Simulated models at the level of Proof of Concept) introduced building blocks and data sources applicable to the Living Labs. However, the current phase of the project focuses on practical information utilization. Accordingly, new building blocks and data sources relevant to the LL will be detailed, while previously collected ones will be briefly presented with references to detailed descriptions, as indicated in Section 6.

In Section 5, an initial set of resilience and agility strategies for Inland Water Transport (IWT) infrastructures within intermodal chains, encompassing climate adaptation measures for the medium/long term and short-term ad-hoc agility measures, has been developed. These strategies will undergo evaluation within the Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF) to identify and prioritize actions in the Living Labs. Additionally, they will be integrated into the development of What-if scenarios within WP1 to assess the implementation of climate adaptation measures, enhancing resilience and sustainability. Furthermore, these strategies will support the definition and implementation of stress tests, particularly for extreme weather situations.

Throughout the project's progression, the RSQF will be established to enable quantification based on developed model characteristics within the whole project. This entails identifying and developing KPIs and metrics covering sustainability and resilience, accompanied by cost-benefit analyses. These analyses will establish current baselines for the Living Labs and validate comparisons with the application of ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies, and other innovations.

Conclusions and further steps will be presented in Section 7.

1.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

Table 1 maps the ReNEW's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

<p>Deliverable D1.2: Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v2</p> <p>Resilience and Sustainability Models and Simulation Libraries, Data sources 2nd Release, Strategies 1st Release</p>
<p>Task T1.1: Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks</p> <p>Provide the building blocks serving as baseline supporting: the planning, operation and evaluation and the impacts assessment of FMP and autonomous barges; the Digital Twins as well as the assessment and benchmarking of Emissions Neutral Solutions as these will be tested in the LL scenarios</p>

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions (continued)

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST1.1.1 Hazards and vulnerabilities in IW Transport	Define risks and hazards to IWT as part of intermodal chains. Identify, profile and catalogue factors like extreme climate events, low water, floods, ice, technical and human failures, and infrastructural bottlenecks in IWT, connected to long distance and urban scenarios per the Living Labs requirements. Consider also covering physical and cyberthreats similarly to technical and human failures, and their consequences and impacts to the IWT system. Create a threat scenarios catalogue based on known (past) threats, and on possible (future) threats with analysis (ranking) of cascading effects, frequency and impact strengths, and their relevance to the LLs.	Further analysis and refinement of vulnerabilities and consequences in Section 2
ST1.1.2 Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities	<p>Describe Models and IT tools for networks, traffic and bottlenecks, emissions etc. Network models will include IWT and multimodal routing, infrastructures as seaports and terminals and inland ports. Models will be capturing the operational characteristics of IWT network and infrastructures, including environmental aspects as seasonality in draught and river flows.</p> <p>To support mitigation scenarios, transshipment and interoperability with rail and road transport will be covered, identifying terminals and relevant infrastructures, and further refined in ST1.2 through semantic models and Knowledge Graph. ReNEW will reuse and extend IW-NET developed models for strategies such as collaborative port and locks solutions for e.g., low water scenarios and corridor management. Environmental and life-cycle aspects will also be considered for terminal infrastructures and vessel models (ship engines, stern and bow rudders), including emission (CO₂, SO_x, NO_x, PM) models based on fuel consumption in moving/hotel mode, tide/current, sailing restrictions, routing on IWT, fairway water depth and flow rate, upstream/downstream including currents and tides calculations.</p> <p>Tools will fully support Web-GIS visualisation. Simulation tools will allow tests of new technologies, resilience, and agility strategies. Additionally, hydrological models and tools will assist in the assessment concerning navigability on waterways. Identify, analyse, and link data sources for the models and the simulation tools and the evaluation of the ReNEW LL scenarios and measures, including transport networks and infrastructures (capacities and costs), commodities and cargo flows (origin/destination matrices, amounts per commodity), routes. Access and link TEN-T network data, and inland ENC data for European countries according to the European inland ECDIS standard (CESNIEU Standards Committee for the Inland Navigation Domain), and traffic data on locks and waterway segments</p>	<p>As this deliverable is the second of the three versions,</p> <p>The first release of models and tools have been identified in the previous D1.1 (and in D3.6 and D3.8), the list was updated and an overview of all building blocks, data sources, libraries etc. was presented in Section 6.</p> <p>The Cost-Benefit-Analysis Model is described in Section 4.2.</p>

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions (continued)

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST1.1.3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs and metrics	<p>Develop joint/correlated resilience and sustainability indicators to enable their quantification based on the developed model characteristics. Deliver a Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF) which facilitates quantification of system resilience coupled with a multi-objective optimisation approach, constrained by the necessary condition of positive correlation between measures to enhance resilience and sustainability characteristics, to aid appropriate and optimal decision making in the IWT context.</p> <p>The RSQF considers the dynamic nature of the problem, and in this regard a dynamic equilibrium restricted assignment model is proposed to simulate system(s) performance evolution. The temporal dimension (i.e. short and longer term impacts), associated with the progressive response of the system(s) to a time-varying impact requires that the analysis formulation of the system(s) response and the assessment of its corresponding resilience require such a dynamic approach which takes into consideration aspects of the perturbation, as well as the system impedance, i.e. resistance to alter its previous state due to the actual capacity of adaptation to the changes and the state of knowledge of the current situation, the system(s) dependency/interdependency, capacity building systems, and the evolving stress level.</p> <p>Moreover, the uncertainty involved in the system hyper-parameters, e.g., system(s) redundancy, impedance, adaptability, and vulnerability, are incorporated in the RSQF. Develop a set of resilience and sustainability measures, KPIs, and metrics accounting for economic, ecological, and socio-economic factors to support cost-benefit analysis to help establishing current baselines for the LLs and will let comparison with the application of the ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies, and other innovations.</p>	<p>A Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework will be created in the further course of the project (i.e., in the further versions of the deliverable). The initial methodology is described, further evaluation and plans with regard to the KPIs are presented in Section 3, as well as the key elements reached for the RSQF. The structure of the planned CBA is explained in Section 4</p>
ST1.1.4 Resilience and Agility strategies	<p>Develop a set of strategies on resilience and agility for IWT infrastructures as part of intermodal chains including climate adaptation (medium/long term) and agility (short-term, ad-hoc) measures. These strategies will subsequently be evaluated as a part of the RSQF to identify/prioritise actions in the Living Labs. What-if scenarios will be developed to evaluate the implementation of climate adaptation measures to increase resilience and sustainability; stress tests will be defined/implemented e.g., concerning extreme weather situations.</p> <p>For the selection of the most relevant for ReNEW strategies a serious gaming approach will also be introduced supported by a (real time) resilience dashboard (adapted from the one developed in the H2020 PRECINCT project). Based on specific climate change related scenarios, cooperative resilience strategies will be developed during role-play games, considering different options of shifting routes, modes, schedules, and specific uses of vessel enabled solutions including Autonomy and modular Platforms (WP2).</p>	<p>The first release of strategies is provided in Section 5.</p>

2 Hazards and Vulnerability Scenario Catalogue

Creating a Hazards and Vulnerability Scenario Catalogue in D1.1. was a first step to get an overview of potential threats and hazards that may occur in IWT.

The Hazards and Vulnerabilities Scenarios Catalogue categorizes various threats and hazards into five key areas: Labour oriented/Pandemic, natural phenomenon events (such as low and high-water periods, ice), crime, cyber-attacks, operational disruption events, and other disruption events, including 57 identified hazards and threats.

Project partners responsible for the LLs have assessed these events, evaluating their relevance, impact strength, and likelihood of occurrence. This comprehensive evaluation provides an understanding of the potential consequences linked to the identified threats, hazards, risks, and vulnerabilities. Beyond being a repository of information, the catalogue serves as a baseline for creating what-if scenarios and a further analyse of the most important events.

2.1 Conducting Risk Analysis for Relevant Events

Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) is one of the principal components of Supply Chain Resiliency. To improve the resilience of IWT, suitable mitigation measures have to be deployed to reduce the impact of disruptive events. For the identification of these measures, the Living Labs evaluated several threats and hazards regarding their relevance. Afterward, only the most relevant ones, which are also suitable for what-if scenarios were selected for further investigations. Last, for these threats and hazards measures were identified and analysed. Consequently, only a selection of all mitigation measures is listed. Threats and hazards which are not rated as important shall not be ignored but monitored and should be evaluated later.

The methodology for risk analysis begins with the definition of key terms such as assets, threats, and hazards as outlined in D1.1- Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1. It also delineates various risk domains, including operational, climate change, and regulatory aspects. The identification of threats and hazards associated with each asset is covered in D1.1, along with a general overview of vulnerabilities, which are further refined in subsequent sections.

Within the analysis, specific actors and their corresponding assets are considered, such as inland waterway transport (IWT) operators with barges and infrastructure providers with ports. The assessment process involves evaluating the likelihood and consequences (both direct and indirect) of identified risks. Therefore, a framework was established as described in D1.1. A matrix has been developed in *D1.8- ReNEW Methodology Specification for Resilience and Sustainability v1* (starting with page 37) in the Section "Risk Management" to quantify risk by multiplying likelihood and consequences, a task intended for completion in upcoming deliverables of Work Package 1 (WP1).

Figure 1: Supply Chain Risk Management Cycle (adopted from Norman, A. & Jansson, U. [1])

As shown in Figure 1 the risk management cycle, integral to the methodology, follows a systematic approach:

- Identification of risks
- Assessment of the identified risks
- Mitigation of risks, emphasizing the identification and assessment of strategies to manage the risks and their implementation.
- Monitoring risks, featuring regular checks on the chain on additional risks, changing likelihood and consequences as well as the performance of implemented mitigation strategies.

The first set of strategies is presented in the current deliverable, with further refinement anticipated in subsequent WP1 deliverables. The discussion component delves into the uniqueness of risk analysis in the inland waterway transport domain. Notably, the IWT domain is recognized for its complexity, involving diverse actors each exposed to distinct risks and employing varying risk management strategies. This complexity is exemplified in the contrast between logistics operators and infrastructure providers, each navigating specific challenges and implementing tailored risk strategies.

2.2 Analysis of Event Consequences and Vulnerabilities

To create a safe and resilient living lab environment, as a first step, an initial assessment was conducted by LLs in order to identify the most important threats and hazards, that can be found in D1.1. However, further prioritization and deeper analysis of key events were necessary.

In this chapter, the threats and hazards were further analysed from different aspects, using practical examples of consequences and vulnerabilities, or potential damage costs. For this purpose, desk research was conducted. Furthermore, in order to gain a better understanding of the threats and to understand the context of the living lab environment, the partners responsible for the living labs provided further information. This approach aims to help living labs develop resilience strategies.

2.2.1 Shortage of Skills and Labour

Shortage of skills and labour are assessed as relevant or medium relevant by most living labs. A lack of skilled people in the transportation industry can lead to major problems for the overall economy, which depends on a well-functioning and efficient transport system [2]. Furthermore, a shortage of skills can result in delays and a reduction in the overall efficiency of inland waterway transport.

Shortage of skills can often be linked to Shortage of labour. Independent entrepreneurs in inland water transport often choose their careers based on family background. The growing fleet capacity and changing operational modes have increased the demand for hired nautical personnel, resulting in a shortage of qualified professionals [3]. In this respect, LL4 will apply AI driven navigation, for a vessel that is designed to be autonomous, i.e., to have no crew on board during transit. In this way, it will be possible to reduce the negative consequences of the increasingly pronounced lack of skills and labour.

There are different consequences because of a shortage of skills, first of all, lack of safety and financial loss: For example, machine breakdowns from inadequate maintenance can lead to high-cost repairs. Lifting injuries may occur due to insufficient training on proper handling. Electric shocks may happen due to a lack of training in equipment operation. Inadequate training in handling dangerous material can result in chemical burns [4].

According to LL1, the tools developed in ReNEW can be deployed in any disaster or flood area in Europe after a disaster has occurred. This involves working with a scenario in which the operational people, who operate a terminal, fail. That is, the last surviving "manager" of the site must be the most highly qualified. In this case, the functions that have failed must be taken over by him/her (steering and mooring of the ship, loading the vessel, operating the crane, etc.). Vulnerabilities that can lead to negative consequences include insufficiently trained personnel, insufficiently qualified personnel, too little practice on the field, too little practical experience, teams that are not coordinated with each other, lack of maintenance of the equipment, lack of equipment, etc.

LL2 mentioned Crew Shortages and Staffing Challenges, which refer to situations where there is an insufficient number of qualified personnel to operate and manage vessels effectively. As vulnerabilities, they listed Industry Attrition and Global Events Impacting Mobility. Industry Attrition

means high turnover rates and challenges in attracting and retaining skilled crew members. Global Events Impacting Mobility refers to global events, such as pandemics, impacting the mobility and availability of maritime personnel. Regarding the negative consequences, operational disruptions may occur, i.e., shortages leading to disruptions in navigation schedules and increased workload on existing staff. As another consequence, LL2 mentioned increased safety risks due to insufficient staffing levels.

According to LL2, operational delays and disruptions caused by crew shortages lead to economic losses. They mentioned also Recruitment and Training Expenses, i.e., costs associated with recruiting and training new crew members to address shortages.

According to LL3, this event category is not covered by the route planner they plan to implement, however, they mentioned the fact that IWT has many small SMES where the boat master is the owner of the vessels. These vessels are also manned with mobile crew.

According to LL1, the costs of the damage due to a shortage of skills and labour are difficult to estimate. If one of the people in the team or one of the parts of the machinery that has to intervene fails to perform his/her job, the entire operation can go completely wrong.

2.2.2 Storm, Tornado, Strong Wind, Hailstorm and Thunderstorm

In inland waterway transport, vessels are generally stable against wind impact, but at specific locations or for certain vessel types, strong winds can pose risks. For instance, some inland container vessels may face flooding and container sliding at a mean wind speed of 18 m/s [5]. “Open cargo holds may flood and unlash empty containers located on the upper tiers may start sliding” [6]. Furthermore, the typical effects on ports are delays due to interruptions in loading and unloading procedures, and direct damage to infrastructure. E.g., the recommended maximum wind speed for crane operations is around 18 m/s depending on the crane design [5].

Vessel manoeuvrability can be compromised, leading to collisions with waterway infrastructure and other vessels, e.g., when entering locks. This can result in additional repair work and high costs. In 2007, the container vessel M/V Excelsior nearly capsized on the Rhine due to improperly stored containers, causing a six-day navigation suspension and impacting around 500 vessels. Furthermore, 32 containers were lost [6].

2.2.3 Flood, High Waters, Heavy Rain

In the event of severe flooding, interruptions to IW services may occur. However, despite more frequent and prolonged flooding periods, floods are expected to be less disruptive than droughts since their impacts are relatively short period. [7]. For example, the River Rhine has three defined thresholds for high flow levels that impact navigation. The Lower Threshold stops selected ship types and limits the speed of the remaining ships. It also concentrates traffic in the center of the fairway to reduce wave stress on the lateral infrastructure. When the water level reaches the Higher Threshold, navigation is generally stopped, with few exceptions. The motivation behind this threshold is to protect the infrastructure and ensure the security of navigation. High flow velocities associated with

discharges above HSW-II reduce the maneuverability of vessels traveling downstream. Finally, exceeding the General Stoppage threshold leads to a complete stoppage of navigation to prevent accidents and damage to the vessels and infrastructure [8].

High river flow velocities and strong eddies during flood events hinder or halt navigation, leading to additional expenses for freight companies. During the 2019 floods of the Mississippi River, the river height at Baton Rouge (Louisiana) remained above flood levels for 221 days, leading to a 25% reduction in the transport of commodities in the river [9].

Floods increase bank erosion, scouring, seepage, or overflowing, and pose a threat to the stability and integrity of embankments, supports, and other IWT components. Furthermore, the capacity of culverts, weirs, and sluices may be compromised by the heightened flow levels. Furthermore, floodwaters typically carry a higher amount of debris, necessitating additional efforts for debris removal from screens and areas behind structures. Additionally, the heightened demands placed on locks and sluices during flood events can result in increased wear and tear on these facilities due to their use in facilitating floodwater conveyance. In fact, the use of navigation infrastructure (e.g. canal embankments) for flood risk management introduces its own set of challenges and considerations [10].

Even where the total economic contribution of water transportation is relatively small compared to other sectors, its multiplier effects are substantial. A study [11] of the IWT system closure in Oklahoma due to flooding showed that the economic impact increased nonlinearly as the duration of the closure extended, with regions more reliant on the agricultural sector being most affected.

Figure 2: Overview of inland waterways in Europe [7]

“From the per grid comparison of the maximum depths for the 100-year return period and the 10-year return period, it is estimated that the difference of high water levels will exceed 5m for 344.45 km out of the 17419.30 km of the navigable network”. The relevant segments of the network are highlighted in red in Figure 2. Additionally, there is a forecasted rise in the frequency of floods over time. In this respect, the mean annual exceedance frequency of the current 100 year return period peak flow is

projected to increase by 176% in Europe by the end of the century while in certain countries such as the Netherlands, the increase will be significantly higher [7].

The usability of the waterway is also limited due to the lack of bridge clearance.

LL3 claimed that, based on predictions, they expect that in 2050 this will be 5% less frequent than now because of climate change. The consequences they singled out are safety issues and longer sailing times.

LL2 mentioned heavy rainfall, melting snow, or storms that can lead to river flooding, causing water levels to rise rapidly. The vulnerabilities they singled out are insufficient infrastructure resilience and inadequate monitoring systems. Insufficient infrastructure resilience refers to vulnerable infrastructure, such as locks and dams, that may lack resilience to accommodate sudden increases in water levels. Inadequate monitoring systems refer to a lack of real-time monitoring systems to detect rising water levels promptly and communicate warnings to vessels. According to LL2, there are a few negative consequences, such as Navigation Disruptions and Infrastructure Damage. Navigation Disruptions refer to immediate disruptions to vessel navigation due to submerged infrastructure or unsafe conditions. Infrastructure Damage refers to damage to locks, dams, and riverbanks due to the force of floodwaters.

LL2 singled out the following costs: Infrastructure Repair and Economic Losses. Infrastructure Repair refers to costs associated with repairing and restoring damaged locks, dams, and other navigation infrastructure.

Economic Losses refer to financial losses for industries due to halted transportation and supply chain disruptions.

Regarding the existing strategies, LL2 mentioned Early Warning Systems and Resilient Infrastructure. Early Warning Systems refer to the implementation of advanced monitoring and early warning systems to detect rising water levels and provide timely alerts. Resilient Infrastructure refers to investment in resilient infrastructure that can withstand the impact of floods, such as reinforced embankments and flood-resistant locks. The hydrological model of the river, proposed in LL2, will help to anticipate, alert, and take early action in case of floods.

LL1 made a difference between:

- Flood/heavy rain in the province of Liege,
- Flood in general in Flanders and
- Floods in Europe.

2.2.3.1 Flood in the Province of Liege

According to LL1, vulnerabilities that led to negative consequences are the following: The breach of a dam due to heavy rainfall, coupled with a water bomb and poor preparation by the government. According to hydrologist Patrick Willems (KUL), up to 1.5 million litres of water per second fell on Belgian territory. Several records were broken locally, especially in Verviers. Normally 75 mm of water per m² per 24 hours is required to qualify as a “natural disaster”. Here 100 mm fell in 6 hours [12].

Tilff, in de provincie Luik. © BELGA

Figure 3: Flood in the province of Liege on 15.07.2021

Effects/consequences: 39 dead people, 11 missing, 12,000 persons homeless – 48,000 buildings damaged (from which 45,000 houses) – 11,000 cars damaged – 9,670 hectares under water [13], [14], [15].

LL1 focused on costs in the province of Liege. The damage from 2021 summer's flood disaster has risen to 2.164 billion euros, spread over more than 70,000 damage cases. This is evident from a new estimate from the insurers. In Wallonia alone, costs exceed 2 billion euros. The most financially affected municipality is Liège, with more than 200 million euros in damage. In Flanders, Voeren was hit hardest, with 4.4 million euros in damage.

2.2.3.2 Floods in General in Flanders

According to the LL1, the risk zones for flooding correspond to the areas that have been flooded in the past more than twice in ten years, together with areas that, according to flood models, flood every 25 years or more. Moreover, there must be at least 30 cm that has been reached or is forecast.

The following map shows the list of areas that have been flooded in the past 10 years – the main reasons for this were: lowlands, large surfaces that are paved, poor water drainage.[16]

Figure 4: Map of Flanders [17]

According to the LL1, the Warning system of the Flemish government is implemented: www.waterinfo.be

It is a website of the Flemish government with information about possible floods and drought. All measurements and predictions are brought together here. This way, the necessary measures can be taken to minimize water damage. The solutions LL1 develops in the ReNEW project are mainly actions and plans after the occurrence of a disaster, such as floods, forest fires, etc. Preventing these calamities and warning the population is a task of the government. It does this through stimulating initiatives, but also punitive and corrective measures.

2.2.3.3 Floods in Europe

According to the LL1, the casualties of 2021 floods in Europe are the following [18], [19], [20], [21], [22]:

- Total: minimum 224 deaths,
- Germany: 180,
- Belgium: 41,
- Austria: 1
- Romania: 2

LL1 mentioned the European Emergency Response Coordination Centre, officially the Emergency Response Coordination centre (ERCC), which is the European Union's executive agency for civil protection. It coordinates assistance to disaster-affected countries, including relief supplies, expertise, civil protection teams and specialized equipment. The center facilitates the rapid deployment of emergency aid and serves as a coordination point among all EU Member States, the 10 other participating countries, the affected country and experts in the field of civil protection and

humanitarian aid [23]. The ERCC works 24/7 and is available to support any country, whether within or outside the EU, that is impacted by a significant disaster upon the request of national authorities or a UN body [23].

The tools developed in ReNEW can be deployed in any disaster or flood area in Europe after a disaster has occurred.

2.2.4 Drought, Low Waters, Heat, Dry Warm Periods

Reduced flow levels can hinder both navigation and water supply. Additionally, low flow diminishes groundwater recharge and impacts groundwater quality. A rise in air temperatures contributes to higher water temperatures, which, combined with low flow, can trigger numerous ecological and chemical alterations in water bodies [24].

When water levels fall below a certain point, barges cannot fully use their maximum draught (the vertical distance between the waterline and the bottom of the hull), reducing cargo capacity. “As a result, more vessels have to be operated or ships have to wait until water levels will rise or the total amount to be transported has to be reduced in absolute values” [25]. Additionally, prices are expected to have a negative relationship with water levels under certain demand conditions [25].

In 2022, low water conditions significantly affected inland waterway transport. The number of critical low water days increased compared to 2021 but was still lower than the 2018 peak. This led to a notable +42.5% average increase in freight rates across various cargo types. Dry bulk and container freight rates have been on the rise since 2020 due to recovery demand (because of the Pandemic), which was further accentuated in 2022 by booming coal transport, the transfer of vessel capacity from the Rhine to the Danube region, and low waters [26].

According to LL3, based on predictions, they expect that in 2050 low water will be 15% more frequent than now due to climate change. As a consequence, they mentioned problems in the navigability of the river, and the vessel that need to be loaded in lower capacity.

According to LL2, droughts in inland navigation involve prolonged periods of below-average precipitation, leading to reduced water levels in rivers and waterways. They singled out a few vulnerabilities: Lack of Water Management Plans (insufficient planning for managing water levels during periods of low precipitation) and Dependency on Seasonal Water Flow (overreliance on seasonal water flow patterns without effective contingency plans). As the consequences, LL2 mentioned Navigation Restrictions, i.e., reduced water levels that can limit vessel draft, imposing navigation restrictions, and Impact on Lock Operations: Challenges in maintaining sufficient water levels for effective lock operations.

LL2 singled out certain damage costs such as Dredging Expenses (costs associated with dredging to maintain navigable water depths during droughts) and Economic Impact (economic losses due to reduced transportation capacity and increased operational costs).

Regarding the strategies, LL singled out the following: water conservation measures (implementation of water conservation measures to mitigate the impact of reduced water levels), and drought contingency plans (development and implementation of contingency plans for managing navigation during drought conditions). the hydrological model of the river, proposed in II2, will help to anticipate, alert, and take early action in case of droughts.

LL2 mentioned wildfires as a possible hazard or threat, which could also be a result of high temperatures. Wildfires in inland navigation involve uncontrolled fires in the watershed areas of rivers, potentially impacting water quality and causing soil erosion. According to LL2, there are several vulnerabilities related to wildfires:

- Lack of vegetation management: insufficient vegetation management in watershed areas leading to an increased risk of wildfires.
- Ineffective emergency response plans: lack of well-defined plans for responding to wildfires and mitigating their impact on water quality.

As the consequences, LL2 singled out water quality issues (degradation of water quality due to ash and debris runoff into rivers), and navigation restrictions (increased sedimentation and debris flow may lead to navigation restrictions). In this respect, different costs may occur, such as:

- Cleanup Expenses: Costs associated with cleaning up debris and addressing water quality issues.
- Economic Impact: Economic losses due to disrupted navigation and potential damage to vessels.

According to the LL1, Flanders has one of the lowest water availability per inhabitant. This is due to a combination of a high population density and a relatively limited presence of surface and groundwater. Climate change is throwing the existing, fragile balance out of balance. In 1976, 2011, from 2017 to 2020, and in 2022, they already had to deal with extreme drought in Flanders. The increase in temperature causes more evaporation. It will also rain less in the summer, which means that extreme drought may occur more often and more intensely in Flanders in the future [27].

The drought in Flanders is measured by 3 systems [27], [28]: meteorological drought, agricultural drought and hydrological drought.

Meteorological drought: when the balance between precipitation and evaporation shifts. The high-impact climate scenario for Flanders shows that summer precipitation could fall from an average of 194 mm in the current climate to 157 mm (-19%) by 2050. Moreover, at the same time, potential evaporation over the same period could increase from 252 to 279 mm (+11 %).

Agricultural drought occurs when soil moisture levels are too low. In the current climate, the soil moisture content in Flanders only falls below the threshold for about 6 days on average at which crops and vegetation experience the onset of drought stress, which can lead to reduced growth and lower crop yields.

Hydrological drought: The flow rates and lowest water levels in watercourses also come under pressure during drought episodes. This concerns hydrological drought. Scenario analysis for non-navigable waterways reveals that on average in Flanders the number of days with a very low water flow could almost double by 2050: from an average of 18 days now to 32 days. By 2100, this could double again (to 64 days), or an increase by a factor of 4 compared to the current climate. Many watercourses then have a very low flow rate, well below one litre/second, or are even in danger of drying up completely (especially upper courses in sloping areas).

Regarding the consequences, LL1 claimed that in and just after the 2nd heat period (5 to 20 August), significant excess mortality was observed in Belgium (+34.8% or 1,460 additional deaths, on top of the expected 4,198 deaths) in all age groups of the population, but especially in the group of persons over 65 years of age (742 additional deaths in the age group over 85 years and 600 additional deaths in the age group of 65-84 years).

With the IMPACTtool (Klimaatportaal Vlaanderen), designed by the Flemish government, predictions can be made about the droughts for the coming years and the vulnerability are demonstrated in the different areas. Here is a simulation of LL Ghent for the next 80 years, compared to the Flanders area (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

Figure 5: Ghent - drought – number of days/year [29]

Effecten

Rain in total per month

- Current
- High impact 2030
- High impact 2050
- High impact 2075
- High impact 2100

Impacts

Drought - duration (hydrological) in days per year

- Ghent
- Flanders

Number of dry days per year

- Ghent
- Flanders

Figure 6: Ghent area and Flanders; Effects: rain in total mm per month for periods 2030, 2050, 2075 and 2100; Impacts: Drought – duration (hydrological) in days per year – figures for Ghent area and Flanders [29]

Figure 7 illustrates water depth variations in the Rhine at Bingen/Ostrich and associated transportation costs for a large motor cargo vessel (GMS, bulk cargo) from 2002 to 2003. Simulations indicate low costs per ton of cargo in 2002 and the first half of 2003 due to moderate or higher water levels. However, extremely low water levels in the second half of 2003 led to a significant cost increase. The rise in specific transportation costs results from reduced cargo capacity, slower speeds, and longer travel times [6].

Figure 7: Development of water depths at Bingen/Ostrich and specific transportation costs of a large motor cargo vessel (GMS, bulk cargo) presented for the years 2002 (moderate and high water levels) and 2003 (low water). Reproduced by Holtmann and Bialonski (2009)

2.2.5 Ice

Extended periods of temperatures below zero degrees Celsius can lead to the formation of ice, posing risks to navigation signs and waterway infrastructure, for example, “ice jams clogging the lock area or due to freezing of moving parts and mooring devices” (Figure 8). The impact of ice events varies based on the location. Generally, it is anticipated that the consequences for infrastructure will likely lessen in the future due to global warming and rising water temperatures [6].

Figure 8: Locks on the Danube. Source: [6]

Prolonged intense precipitation, either alone or combined with snowmelt, can lead to “increased discharges, flow velocities, and water levels”. In severe instances, this can escalate to flooding, posing a serious threat to both property and human lives [6].

2.2.6 Data Theft, Blackmail, Hybrid Attacks

The company Maersk experienced a cyber-attack in 2017 [30]. The malware had spread to Maersk locations across the globe, entering the systems and phone networks, leading to \$300 million of damage costs [31].

With potential reputational risks, companies may feel compelled to pay ransoms for stolen data. The percentage of companies paying ransoms has risen from 10% in 2019 to 54% in 2022, based on analysis of large losses only (€1mn+). If data are exfiltrated and encrypted, companies are 2.5 times more likely to pay a ransom [32]. The report emphasizes that undetected and uncontained cyber breaches can be up to 1,000 times more expensive than those addressed early. In other words, early detection and response can stop a €20,000 loss turning into a €20mn one [32].

The cyber threat to inland navigation infrastructure, similar to other critical sectors, poses risks of severe traffic disruptions, economic and environmental damages, and costly repairs. Main concerns include potential damage to waterway infrastructure, such as docks and movable bridges, due to improper operation. Water level management equipment, like sluices and locks, could lead to flooding if misused in a cyberattack. The highest disruption risks are associated with IT systems in traffic planning, especially where river authorities operate a vessel traffic service (VTS). The potential impact of an attack emphasizes the need for constant vigilance [33].

LL1 also claimed that a cyberattack can let fail the operation. Vulnerabilities that lead to this are Open Source data, connection via the gateway on the ship and crane, carelessness of the people in the team when using passwords, etc. LL1 recognized the following consequences: failure of the operation, material damage, and people hurt or dying.

According to LL3, this type of event does not apply to their use case.

LL2 mentioned the disruption of traffic management systems (due to a DoS attack). Inland waterways often rely on sophisticated traffic management systems to ensure the safe and efficient movement of vessels. A DoS attack targeting these systems could disrupt communication and coordination, leading to potential collisions or navigation errors. According to LL2, vulnerabilities that may lead to negative consequences are inadequate network security, outdated software and systems, weak authentication mechanisms, insider threats, lack of redundancy and resilience, unsecured communication channels, social engineering attacks, insecure remote access, and inadequate incident response planning. There are also some related consequences mentioned by LL2 such as direct navigation issues: immediate traffic disruption, economic impacts: financial losses, supply chain disruptions: delayed shipments, safety concerns: increased risk of accidents, environmental impact: accidental spills or pollution, legal and regulatory consequences: regulatory violations, public perception and trust: loss of confidence, emergency response challenges: limited response capability, cascading effects on other infrastructure: impact on ports and facilities, regional economic impact: impact on local economies, long-term reputational damage: loss of market confidence, increased cybersecurity concerns: wider cybersecurity threat perception. Furthermore, LL2 singled out the following issues resulting in high costs:

- Immediate operational costs: loss of revenue, operational downtime;
- Supply chain disruptions: inventory costs, production delays;
- Emergency response costs: search and rescue operations, environmental cleanup;
- Legal and regulatory consequences: fines and penalties, legal defense costs;
- Infrastructure repair and maintenance: system restoration costs, infrastructure upgrades;
- Insurance costs: claim payments, premium increases;
- Reputational damage: market share loss;
- Cascading economic impact: regional economic losses, government assistance costs;
- Cybersecurity investments: security infrastructure costs;
- Loss of future opportunities: impact on future projects.

2.2.7 Kidnap/Hostage and Terrorism

In both kidnappings and hostage situations, there are victims that the kidnappers abduct and keep in a certain location. Complying with the demands is expected to prevent harm to the prisoners and eventually lead to the release of some or all of them. "Locations for all types of hostage taking can be on land (e.g. embassy occupation), on water (e.g. piracy) or in the air (e.g. hijackings)" [34].

There is also a situation termed "held hostage," where cargo in transit is withheld by the driver or carrier/broker until their demands are met. Late arrivals can incur substantial fees, sometimes

reaching up to \$1,000, a significant portion of the overall compensation for the load. The driver may retain the load until the carrier and receiver agree to waive the late fee [35].

2.2.8 Outbreak of War

Direct attacks on infrastructure, including ports, bridges, etc. are frequently the result of war. This can hinder the flow of people and cargo by destroying important transportation network components. To avoid or minimize negative consequences, increased security measures are required, which can lead to high costs.

There are also possible consequences from the environmental side. Pollutants may be released into inland waterways, e.g., oil spills, chemical contamination, barge sinkings, which impact water quality, etc. Furthermore, inland waterways may be used as an escape, placing additional strain on already overburdened transportation networks and making it more difficult to provide supplies. Nevertheless, loss of life is one of the biggest consequences of war, including employees who must be available despite possible constant attacks or people who live nearby.

There is no data about costs in real-time, however, there are different types of costs that could be considered: Costs of Infrastructure reconstruction, recovery costs, costs arising from loss of vessel and cargo, insurance costs, etc.

2.2.9 Cargo Theft, Sabotage, Corruption, and Insider Crime

Rail and inland waterway movements are less prone to theft compared to road infrastructure [36]. The techniques used by individuals involved in cargo theft are various such as [37]:

1. Deceptive practices: Cargo thieves may assume the identity of legitimate carriers or utilize forged documentation to gain entry to shipments.
2. Hijacking: Criminals may physically intercept control of cargo during transit, often using force or threats.
3. Insider collaboration: In certain instances, individuals within the supply chain may cooperate with thieves, supplying information or facilitating access to shipments.

Apart from global cargo theft trends, other risks such as supply chain corruption, drug smuggling, and disruptions to business continuity can contribute to cargo losses. These issues not only create opportunities for cargo crime but can also, cause delays in shipment progress and, result in a complete loss of cargo due to compromised shipment integrity [38]. For example, despite COVID-19 restrictions, criminals adapted their methods, leading to record drug seizures at Rotterdam and Antwerp ports. Dutch customs seized 48 tons, and Belgian customs seized 65.5 tons of drugs, with insider involvement reported [38].

LL2 mentioned intentional or accidental blockade of locks and dams. This threat involves the deliberate or unintentional obstruction of locks and dams, critical components of waterway infrastructure. Vulnerabilities related to this threat are various such as insufficient surveillance systems, ineffective monitoring, inadequate cybersecurity measures, limited physical security infrastructure, inadequate emergency response planning, and unpreparedness for blockades. Some

consequences were also singled out such as direct navigation disruptions (immediate traffic halt), environmental concerns (altered water flow), and safety risks (navigation accidents). LL2 mentioned the following costs regarding the aforementioned threat:

- Immediate Operational Costs: Loss of Revenue, Operational Downtime;
- Supply Chain Disruptions: Inventory Costs, Production Delays;
- Emergency Response Costs: Search and Rescue Operations, Environmental Cleanup;
- Infrastructure Repair and Maintenance: System Restoration Costs, Infrastructure Upgrades;
- Insurance Costs: Claim Payments, Premium Increases.

2.2.10 Technical Breakdown / Faulty of Instrumentation

Vulnerabilities related to technical breakdowns or faults in instrumentation within inland waterway transport can pose significant challenges. For example, if a primary system fails, the lack of alternatives could result in extended downtime and disruptions.

Aging vessels and infrastructure may be more prone to technical failures. Improper management of aging equipment concerning its anticipated lifespan may lead to preventable safety incidents as well as problems with reliability and maintenance. Extending the useful life of equipment can put an operating facility at risk, as most equipment has a set lifespan. Extended shutdowns occur when older systems and instruments lack the diagnostic technology, necessary to query or troubleshoot the operating problem [39].

LL1 mentioned the following example: the grid is shut down systems will fall out; parts get broken due to bad maintenance or end of life.

There are numerous and various costs that could be included, such as labour costs (due to the increased need for special skills, which can lead to high costs), the cost of purchasing new equipment or instruments, insurance costs, etc. If a technical breakdown or faulty of instrumentation causes spills, leaks, etc., there are also costs of contamination clean-up.

2.2.11 Fault or Unavailability of AIS

AIS (Automatic Identification System) security faces three major threats [40]:

- Spoofing: Involves creating fake ships with false information.
- Hijacking: Manipulating existing AIS station data.
- Availability Disruption: This can be performed only in radiofrequency. As a result, the attacker can disable AIS systems on a large scale.

LL1 also recognized the consequences such as being impossible to steer, the vessel being off the map, etc. In this respect, failure of AIS can damage the operation.

Another threat is Global Positioning System (GPS) jamming, causing inaccuracies in data or lack of data. The jamming may impact the vessels and shore-based infrastructure, since vessel traffic services rely on AIS to some extent. It is concluded that various vessels respond diversely to GPS

jamming, likely attributed to the use of equipment from different manufacturers and different ways of equipment integration [41].

2.2.12 Energy Breakdown

According to LL2, energy breakdown or failure refers to the disruption or failure of the energy supply systems that power essential infrastructure and operations in inland navigation, including locks, dams, and communication systems. LL2 mentioned various vulnerabilities that could lead to negative consequences:

- **Dependence on a Single Power Source:** Overreliance on a single energy source without sufficient backup systems.
- **Insufficient Maintenance:** Lack of regular maintenance and upgrades to energy infrastructure, increasing the risk of system failures.

Furthermore, the consequences that can occur are the following: navigation disruptions (interruptions to navigation operations as energy-dependent systems, such as locks and communication systems, become inoperable), and communication breakdowns (loss of communication between vessels, control centers, and other stakeholders, impacting coordination and safety). As a result, LL2 claimed that high costs can occur, such as:

- **Infrastructure Repair:** Costs associated with repairing energy infrastructure and restoring functionality to locks and communication systems.
- **Operational Downtime:** Economic losses due to the downtime of navigation operations and potential disruptions to the supply chain.

2.2.13 Illegal Wastewater Dumping

According to LL2, illegal wastewater dumping involves the unauthorized discharge of pollutants, contaminants, or untreated wastewater into inland waterways, posing environmental and navigational hazards. In this respect, there are also some vulnerabilities which could lead to unexpected consequences:

- **Lack of Surveillance:** Inadequate surveillance and monitoring systems to detect and prevent illegal dumping activities.
- **Weak Enforcement:** Insufficient enforcement measures and penalties for those engaged in illegal wastewater dumping.

Some of the mentioned consequences are environmental pollution (contamination of water bodies with hazardous substances, threatening aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity), and health risks (increased health risks for communities living along waterways and for those dependent on water resources). Several types of costs can result from this threat, such as:

- **Environmental Remediation:** Costs associated with cleaning and remediation efforts to restore the affected ecosystem.
- **Public Health Costs:** Expenses related to addressing health issues and medical treatments resulting from exposure to contaminated water.

2.2.14 Accidents

Accidents can occur in inland navigation as a result of technical defects or, as with any human activity, due to human error [42]. In the worst case, ship accidents can result in people being injured or even killed. Shipping accidents could also lead to massive economic damage as a result of closures lasting days [43].

LL3 mentioned the TMS Waldhof incident in January 2011. TMS Waldhof capsized and ran aground opposite the port of Loreley. During the salvaging operation, the Rhine was non-navigable for more than 32 days. The vulnerabilities that led to this accident were unstable loading of the vessel and high water levels. LL3 listed the following consequences: delays, rerouting and waiting costs of cargo, costs for alternative transport and transshipment, human casualties, and vessel and cargo casualties.

LL3 assessed the following costs that can occur during the accident:

- Human casualties, vessel, cargo, salvage: 5 – 10 million euros
- Delay costs vessel owners/operators: ca. 19 million euros
- Rerouting & waiting costs cargo: ca. 5 million euros
- Costs of alternative transport, and transshipment: ca. 24 million euros

LL2 mentioned another example of an accident, i.e., communications breakdown in inland waterway traffic management, which involves the sudden or prolonged disruption of communication systems essential for coordinating vessel movements, ensuring safety, and facilitating the flow of goods. They singled out the following vulnerabilities:

- Technical failures: equipment malfunctions;
- Cybersecurity threats: cyber-attacks;
- Lack of redundancy: single points of failure;
- Frequency interference: external interference;
- Inadequate infrastructure resilience: vulnerability to natural disasters.

As consequences, LL2 listed the following:

- Direct operational disruptions: immediate navigational challenges;
- Safety hazards: increased risk of collisions;
- Delayed emergency response: impaired emergency communication;
- Supply chain disruptions: delayed shipments.

Furthermore, according to LL2, costs that could occur are various, such as:

- Immediate operational costs: loss of revenue;
- Supply chain disruptions: increased logistics costs;
- Emergency response costs: search and rescue operations;
- Infrastructure repair and upgrades: restoration costs;
- Insurance claims: claims for damages.

LL2 gave another example of the accident: Vessel Grounding. It occurs when a ship unintentionally runs aground, coming into contact with the riverbed. They mentioned several vulnerabilities related to this threat:

- Insufficient Navigational Information: Lack of up-to-date navigational charts and information about the river's bathymetry.
- Human Error: Errors in navigation due to factors such as fatigue, lack of training, or misinterpretation of navigational aids.

They singled out potential consequences such as navigation delays (disruption to the flow of traffic as grounded vessels impede the movement of other ships, and vessel damage (potential damage to the grounded vessel, requiring repairs). In this respect, various costs can occur such as vessel repairs (costs associated with repairing the grounded vessel) and economic impact (economic losses due to delays in transportation and potential damage to cargo).

2.2.15 Impact of Convenience Flags to Circumvent National Legislation

LL2 mentioned the use of convenience flags—flags of countries with less stringent regulations or enforcement— in inland navigation to avoid complying with the laws of the vessel owner's home country.

They singled out several vulnerabilities such as:

- Weak flag state oversight: lack of stringent oversight and enforcement by the flag state of convenience.
- Lack of international cooperation: limited cooperation between countries to address vessels operating under convenience flags.

There are also various consequences such as regulatory evasion (evasion of national regulations and standards, potentially compromising safety and environmental protection), and unfair competition (unfair competition with vessels operating under more stringent national regulations).

According to LL2, different types of costs could occur:

- Environmental cleanup: costs associated with environmental cleanup if convenience-flagged vessels cause pollution incidents.
- Competitive disadvantage: economic losses for vessels adhering to strict national regulations facing unfair competition.

3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework and Key Performance Indicators

This section refers to subtask ST1.1.3 Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs and metrics. The objective of this task is to create joint/correlated sustainability and resilience indicators in order to enable their quantification based on the proposed model characteristics, as stated in the Grant Agreement.

A framework for quantifying resilience and sustainability (RSQF) is to be provided. This framework facilitates the quantification of system resilience in conjunction with a multi-level optimization approach. The approach is constrained by the necessary condition of a positive correlation between resilience improvement measures and sustainability characteristics. The aim is to support appropriate and optimal decision making in the context of IWT (Inland Waterway Transport). Since the situation is dynamic, the RSQF takes this into account.

To simulate the evolution of system performance, a dynamic equilibrium model with constrained assignment is proposed. This is a model in traffic and transportation planning that deals with the dynamic assignment of traffic flows. The term "equilibrium" is used to indicate that the model takes into account the interactions between different road users and modes in a given system. "Dynamic" means that the model analyses and reacts to changes in traffic behaviour over time. It therefore considers not only the current situation, but also the development over time. The term "Restricted Assignment" indicates that certain limitations or restrictions are recognized in the model. These could be traffic restrictions, capacity limits, or other factors that influence the assignment of traffic flows, for example [44].

The mapping of a "Dynamic Equilibrium Restricted Assignment Model" can often be done by using digital twins and simulations (to be developed in WP3).

It is necessary to follow this dynamic approach that takes various aspects into account. These include the disturbance of the system as well as the system impedance, which includes the resistance to a change in the previous state due to the actual adaptability to changes and the level of knowledge about the current situation. It also includes the dependency and interdependency of the systems, capacity building systems and the evolving stress level. This holistic approach is necessary to capture the temporal dimension, including short- and longer-term effects. This is particularly important to understand the progressive response of the system to time-varying influences.

The RSQF will also deal with the uncertainty associated with the hyper-parameters¹ [45] of the system. These include factors such as redundancy, impedance, adaptability and vulnerability. Resilience and sustainability measures are developed to support a comprehensive cost-benefit analysis and at the same time establish current reference values for performance. This includes the definition of key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics that consist of economic, environmental and socio-economic factors. These measures enable a comparison with the application of ReNEW concepts, processes, technologies and other innovations.

In the previous version of this deliverable (D1.1), a list of 130 KPIs and metrics was initially provided. After several workshops and consultations with project partners, this list was refined within WP3 - European IWT Data Space and Digital Twin solutions for Resilience and Sustainability to select the most relevant KPIs for each Living Lab (LL), in particular focusing on KPIs that were considered as relevant for the Digital Twin with regard to the respective LL. Corresponding documentation can be found in *D3.8 - Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1* [46].

Moving forward, the next step involves collaborating with partners from WP1 and WP3, as well as the LLs, to classify and further refine the identified KPIs. The goal is to align these KPIs with those specified in the Grant Agreement (GA). The significance of each KPI will be examined, with some potentially serving as metrics for the calculation of other KPIs. This collaborative process aims to establish a meaningful set of KPIs for universal project use. Findings from *D1.8 - ReNEW Methodology Specification for Resilience and Sustainability v1* [47], where the KPIs were already assigned to specific resilience dimensions and phases, and metrics required for the calculation of KPIS will also be taken into consideration.

The KPIs that have been defined in the GA and assigned to all LLs are listed below. However, considering that some KPIs in the GA can be calculated in several ways due to their descriptive nature, it is necessary to better define them. In this respect, some of the KPIs identified in D1.1. are assigned to the KPIs based on the GA as examples. There may also be double or multiple assignments. Furthermore, some KPIs can be “stand-alone” KPIs measuring a certain item but can also be a metric – among others - to calculate another KPI. The following assignments are for illustrative purposes only and will be developed in the further course of the project together with the WP1 and WP3 partners as well as the project partners from the individual LL.

¹ “A hyper-parameter is a parameter that influences the configuration of a model, in contrast to the so-called model parameters, which are learned through the training itself. Hyper-parameters are set before the actual training of a model and remain constant during the training process. Their values influence the performance and behavior of the model, and their selection can have a significant impact on the effectiveness of the training.”[44]

3.1 Improved Navigability Capacity

This KPI can have multiple meanings, which proves its descriptive nature. On the one hand, it relates to the improvement of navigation in the sector of inland navigation. On the other hand, it can also measure the extent to which it is easier and more efficient to move around in a certain area - e.g., in a city. This includes improving the navigability of roads through intelligent traffic guidance systems, and the availability of better public transport or pedestrian or cycle paths.

Therefore, in order to better define this KPI from the GA, specific KPIs and metrics are listed below, which could help in calculating Improved Navigability Capacity in the area of inland navigation:

- Fairway depth and width
- Minimum bridge clearance
- Water discharge
- State of floating marks
- Infrastructures status
- Continuity

3.2 Enhanced Land/Sea/Infrastructure Resilience

This KPI (defined in the GA) measures the ability of an area in terms of its resilience. The focus here is on the extent to which the area can withstand or recover from human-made or natural disasters. The resilience of an area can be improved, for example, by ensuring maintenance, adapting, or improving the infrastructure with more robust building materials. However, the establishment or improvement of emergency response systems and the use of secure information technology systems can also ensure the resilience of an area and its infrastructure.

In this respect, in order to better define this descriptive KPI, it is possible to use the following KPIs and metrics:

- State of the port infrastructure
- Availability and condition of the locks
- Status of the bank reinforcements
 - Sedimentation (considering infrastructures)
 - Sediment quantification (considering infrastructures)
 - Erosion (considering infrastructures)
- State of fairway engineering structures (availability, rehabilitation, maintenance, replacement)
- Habitat status
- Indigenous and exogenous species status (Faunal and floral examinations)
- Pollution rate (air, water, noise, soil)
- Minimize the impacts of erosion linked to operation and maintenance [48]²

² This KPI was mentioned in D1.6 and should be taken into account.

3.3 Increase in Modal Shift

The modal shift of a region measures the share of individual modes of transport compared to the total transport volume. In this context, it is desirable to increase the share of environmentally friendly modes of transport such as rail and inland waterway vessels compared to trucks and cars. To ensure this, the relevant mode of transport must be efficient or offer a clear competitive advantage through alternative forms of propulsion, for example, not only from an economic perspective but also in terms of sustainability.

Possible KPIs that could be assigned here are the following:

- Share of freight transport on inland waterway vessels compared to other modes of transport
- Load capacity (compared to other modes of transport)
- Development of the share of passenger transport on inland vessels
- Level Percentage of service
- Continuity
- Shifting capacity
- Percentage of additional revenue (due to recycling etc.)

3.4 Smooth Functioning of Passenger Mobility

This KPI (defined in the GA) measures the extent to which people can move around a certain area without delays or interruptions.

Given that this KPI offers only a descriptive direction, possible KPIs that could be assigned here are the following:

- Punctuality of passenger transportation
- Average travel time for passengers
- Passenger ship occupancy factor
- Continuity

3.5 Reduce Environmental Impact [CO₂e]

On the one hand, this KPI refers to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions generated in a specific area or by specific activities. On the other hand, the reduction of environmental impacts also includes the promotion of sustainable transportation options, the construction of energy-efficient buildings and infrastructure as well as waste avoidance, recycling and resource conservation.

Possible KPIs that could be assigned here are:

- Total direct or indirect emissions of greenhouse gases by weight (emissions in tonnes CO₂e)
- Reduced CO₂ emissions per fleet
- Renewable sources rate

- Pollution rate (air, water, noise, soil)
- ROI related to environmental protection
- Percentage of investments in environmental technology
- Percentage of additional revenue (due to recycling etc.)
- Minimize noise (air and underwater) from the operation and maintenance of infrastructures and vessels [48]³.

Finally, it must be mentioned that the selection of KPIs is also a dynamic process. Depending on the respective situation in the LL and the corresponding scenarios, other KPIs may become relevant that were not previously considered.

It is also conceivable that some of the collected KPIs could be grouped under overarching categories and function as sub-KPIs or metrics. KPIs not only capture risks and their impacts, but also measure the effectiveness of strategies and their economic impact. Economic KPIs, such as the total cost of transporting goods by barge or the average port handling costs, which may be relevant for a cost-benefit analysis (CBA), may need to be included, even if they were not previously considered as relevant.

The CBA approach, described in Section 4, includes the general methodology for the development of CBAs for specific LL scenarios. The assessment and weighting of costs and benefits will incorporate KPIs prioritized by the LL and later the corresponding mitigation strategies and measures in terms of resilience and sustainability based on available data.

³ This KPI was mentioned in D1.6 and should be taken into account.

4 Cost Benefit Analysis

A cost-benefit analysis is an instrument to determine whether a result - the benefit - of an action or measure justifies the effort required for it - the costs. If it can be assumed that benefits and costs are not certain to occur, their expected values, i.e., benefits or costs weighted by their assumed probabilities of occurrence, are used. In the case of the present assessment relevant to ReNEW, the latter is the possible frequency with which the 'disruption' scenarios linked to the LLs could occur.

In general, a cost benefit analysis is based on welfare theory, which states that the goal of each measure is supposed to maximize total welfare to the national society. It can be viewed as a rational and systematic system for assessing actions by expressing all potential consequences in a directly comparable unit of measurement - money. All costs and benefits are managed in the same particular way [49].

4.1 General Methodology

For a cost-benefit analysis, it is useful to distinguish between two situations – the strategic and the tactical level:

4.1.1 Strategic Level: Preparedness for the Disturbance Case

The strategic level is the level to be ready and prepared for a disturbance or emergency situation. This involves comprehensive and proactive planning to ensure that an organization is resilient regarding the occurrence of potential disruptions. At this level, the base for effective response and recovery measures will be set up.

In the following the key components for the strategic level will be described [50], [51], [52], [53], [54]:

Risk Assessment and Analysis:

A thorough analysis of possible disruption scenarios should be carried out. Internal and external factors should also be taken into account. It is also necessary to identify vulnerabilities, dependencies and critical elements that could be affected and suffer damage.

Preparedness Planning:

To be prepared for potential disruptions, a comprehensive emergency plan should be developed, which should also include specific measures, various responsibilities and certain communication strategies. It may be useful to establish clear protocols for the activation of the emergency plan and coordination with relevant authorities.

Resource Allocation:

The resources and materials required for recovery should be identified and made available. Access to important equipment and technology must also be provided. The availability of appropriate personnel needs to be guaranteed.

Training and Drills:

Staff must be trained for emergencies and it must be ensured that they are familiar with their tasks in an emergency situation. To this end, it is necessary to carry out regular exercises, also to check and test the effectiveness of the preparedness plan.

Technology and Infrastructure:

It must be ensured that technical systems and the infrastructure are resilient and can withstand possible disruptions. In this context, it may also be necessary to implement backup systems.

Communication Strategies:

A crisis communication plan should be developed, including methods for disseminating information to the public and the media. In addition, it may be necessary to create communication protocols for internal and external stakeholders. However, this depends on the particular company and its structure and must be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Collaboration and Partnerships:

As already mentioned under Communication Strategies, any planning at the strategic level depends on the company concerned and its structure. In some cases, it may be necessary to create or promote cooperation and partnerships with relevant authorities, organizations and communities. Mutual aid agreements for support in emergency situations may also be useful.

4.1.2 Tactical Level (Reaction to a Disruption Scenario):

At the tactical level, organizations must react to an acute disruption scenario. At this level, the plans and strategies developed at the strategic level should be implemented. The focus at this level is on overcoming the immediate challenges and mitigating the effects of the disruption.

The following key components should be taken into account [55], [52], [56]:

Activation of Emergency Plans:

As soon as an incident or a disruption occurs, the emergency plan developed at the strategic level must be activated immediately. It must also be ensured that all employees are informed of the situation and can perform the tasks assigned to them for this case.

Situation Assessment:

An assessment of the situation should be carried out in real time so that information about the extent and nature of the disruption is available as quickly as possible. In addition, continuous monitoring and updating are necessary in order to be able to react in good time if the disruption develops further.

Resource Mobilization:

The resources and materials made available at the strategic level must be mobilized and deployed immediately. In addition, coordination with external bodies and partners - where defined - must take place in order to obtain additional support if necessary.

Communication Management:

The communication strategies defined in the crisis communication plan must be implemented. In addition, internal and external stakeholders should be informed regularly so that they are always up to date on the situation.

Adaptation of Plans:

Even if various concrete plans are in place, it is important to be flexible and be prepared to adapt the plans depending on how the situation develops. This also includes changing strategies to deal with unexpected problems or changes.

Logistics and Operations:

To ensure the provision of essential services, logistics and operations must be organized efficiently. Measures should also be taken to minimize downtime and prevent or mitigate the impact on critical functions.

Stakeholder Support:

This aspect is also highly dependent on the specific situation or the company concerned and its structure. In general, the intention here is to provide support and assistance to affected stakeholders, including employees, customers and communities. Appropriate strategies must be implemented to meet the immediate needs and concerns of those affected.

By establishing appropriate preparedness measures at a strategic and tactical level, organizations can improve their ability to effectively manage and recover from disruption scenarios. The aspects described above are initially of more theoretical nature and – as already mentioned - can differ significantly depending on the company and structure or the requirements within the individual LL.

Against the background of the ReNEW project, investments can be seen as a form of insurance to improve resilience. The goal is to reduce or eliminate damage costs caused by disturbances by implementing mitigation measures. These cost reductions are classified as benefits. The project aims to analyse the impacts of implementing different resilience strategies and identify the most cost-effective ones in the inland navigation sector.

Implementing mitigation and resilience measures incurs costs, but these investments aim to reduce damage costs. For instance, purchasing and deploying advanced security software to protect against cyberattacks could require an initial investment of several hundred thousand dollars, with ongoing annual maintenance costs of tens of thousands of dollars.

Getting concrete damage costs can be challenging, because costs cannot be estimated precisely or companies refrain from giving too much insight regarding their assets. One approach is to conduct a cost-benefit analysis based on scenarios developed in the ReNEW project and to carry out cost-benefit analyses based on model approaches.

It is important to note that cost estimations can vary widely based on the specific circumstances especially in the case of ReNEW regarding the specific circumstances in the different LL and the nature of the damage, making it crucial to conduct a detailed cost assessment specific to selected scenarios of different LL.

4.1.3 Evaluation of Costs

Regarding the evaluation of costs, we distinguish between direct and indirect costs:

Direct Costs:

These costs are incurred due to physical damages to – for example - port infrastructure. For instance, damages to the quay wall or cranes can result in direct repair and replacement expenses. However, damage to a lock can also cause considerable costs. In February 2018, for example, a container freighter hit a gate in the south chamber of the lock in Kiel-Holtenau on the Kiel Canal (North Sea-Baltic Canal). The salvage and repair work amounted to over 20 million euros [57].

Indirect Costs:

Indirect costs, also referred to as consequential costs, encompass a wide range of expenses resulting from the damage or caused interruptions [58]. For instance:

- **Lost Revenue:** When cargo handling is interrupted due to damage, the affected company may lose substantial revenue. Considering a scenario where a critical failure leads to the temporary halt of cargo handling, resulting in the severe loss in revenue.
- **Salaries:** Even when activities are disrupted, employees may still need to be paid. This ongoing cost can be significant for larger port operations. For example, a two-week interruption due to unforeseen damage may require payroll expenses to be maintained, potentially costing hundreds of thousands of euros.

Each disruption leads to an increase in costs. Avoiding or mitigating the effects of a disruption results in fewer costs, which can then be classified as a benefit. Strategies need to be developed to improve resilience and assess the necessary investments to carry out these strategies. These benefits need to be compared against the expected damage costs.

4.2 Cost-Benefit-Analysis Approach

The general procedure for creating the CBA for selected scenarios for the individual LL is as follows [59], [60], [61]:

- **Define Objectives:** clearly outline the objectives - the goals and desired outcome - of implementing the suggested mitigation measure or strategy.
- **Identify Costs:** estimate all potential costs associated with the implementation of the mitigation measure or strategy and consider ongoing expenses like maintenance, personnel and other costs associated.
- **Quantify Benefits:** Measure and evaluate the positive outcomes and advantages resulting from the suggested measures (e.g. risk reduction, human safety, response time).

- **Economic Advantages:** Assess the financial benefits and positive impacts on economic indicators, such as increased revenue, cost savings, or improved efficiency.
- **Monetary Valuation:** Assign numerical values to costs and benefits to quantify their impact in monetary terms.
- **Timeframe:** Specify the duration over which the mitigation measure or strategy is expected to unfold, including short-term and long-term considerations.
- **Risk Assessment:** Identify and analyse potential risks and uncertainties that could affect the success of the measure or strategy.
- **Sensitivity Analysis:** Examine how variations or changes in key variables may impact the overall outcomes of the suggested measures or strategies.
- **Comparison with Alternatives:** Evaluate the proposed measures or strategies in comparison to alternative solutions or approaches.
- **Decision Criteria:** Establish specific criteria or benchmarks that will be used to make informed decisions about the viability and success.

4.2.1 Living Lab #1: Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronomodality Resilient City Logistics Hub

The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate change on the operations of the City Logistics Hub (CLH). In this living lab new infrastructure will be tested that allows automated sailing and automated mooring, and to build automated loading & unloading systems, managed by a Mobile Command Centre (MCC) as a backup with Shore CC in Antwerp and Rotterdam [47].

Considered as an emergency transport and urban battery with a certain capacity, the resilience-assist modular platform will be used as floating off grid power supply enabling stationary position even in high stream. This ship will be operated as a self-contained sailing ship with a remote control from MCC and will be equipped with hospital accommodation and is expected to feed a hospital with electricity [47].

For a potential scenario involving the use of a Floating Modular Platform (FMP) in response to an emergency caused by an extreme weather event, conducting a cost-benefit analysis can be approached as follows:

Define Objectives:

The objectives of the implementation of the Floating Modular Platform should be clearly defined. These can be minimizing damage, ensuring safety, and facilitating rapid response during extreme weather events.

Identify Costs:

- **Initial Investment:** Estimation of the cost for acquiring and deploying the FMP, including construction, transportation, and installation.
- **Operational Costs:** Consideration of ongoing expenses like maintenance, personnel, and any other recurring costs associated with the FMP's deployment.

Quantify Benefits:

- **Risk Reduction:** Assessment of the potential reduction in damages and losses by deploying the FMP during extreme weather events.
- **Human Safety:** Quantification of the potential lives saved and injuries prevented when having a functional FMP in place.
- **Response Time:** Evaluation of the velocity and efficiency of emergency response facilitated by the FMP compared to alternative measures or solutions.

Monetary Valuation:

Assignment of monetary values to both costs and benefits where possible and depending on the data availability. This may involve the estimation of the economic value of avoided damages and consequences, saved lives, and reduced recovery time.

Timeframe:

Definition of the time horizon for the analysis, considering both short-term and long-term impacts. This could include the lifespan of the FMP and its anticipated effectiveness over a certain period of time.

Risk Assessment:

Identification and assessment of potential risks and uncertainties associated with the implementation of the FMP. Consideration of the likelihood of these risks occurring and their potential impact on costs and benefits.

Sensitivity Analysis:

Execution of sensitivity analyses to explore how changes in key variables (e.g., construction costs, response time, effectiveness) may affect the overall cost-benefit balance.

Comparison with Alternatives:

Comparison of the cost-effectiveness of using the FMP with alternative solutions or scenarios. This could include traditional emergency response methods or other technological solutions.

Decision Criteria:

Specification of clear criteria for decision-making, such as a minimum acceptable benefit-to-cost ratio or a maximum acceptable payback period.

4.2.2 Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway Management

The second living lab of the ReNEW is the Douro living lab. According to ReNEW's objective for resilient and sustainable IWT, the objective of this living lab is to create means to take actions both for illegal wastewater dumping and investigate/simulate the river behaviour in extreme weather conditions [47].

For LL 2, two scenarios are conceivable, for example, a scenario regarding an interruption of port operations due to extreme weather events (drought), making the transport of cargo or passengers impossible.

The second potential scenario could address waste water management and consider the damages to the river/environment when waste water is illegally disposed of.

Scenario 1: Port Disruption Due to Extreme Weather Events

Define Objectives:

- Ensuring of minimal level of service to port operations during extreme weather events.
- Facilitation of quick recovery and resumption of normal activities after the event.

Identify Costs:

- Preventive Measures: Estimation of costs associated with implementing infrastructure improvements and operational changes to withstand extreme weather events.
- Recovery Costs: Assessment of potential expenses for repairing and restoring port facilities after an event.
- Operational Downtime: Quantification of the financial impact of the downtime during the disruption.

Quantify Benefits:

- Operational Continuity: Evaluation of the economic value of maintaining port operations during adverse weather, considering avoided losses and damages.
- Cargo Flow: Assessment of the economic impact of ensuring the timely transportation of cargo.

Monetary Valuation:

Assignment of monetary values to costs and benefits, considering the economic impact on businesses, trade, and the overall economy.

Timeframe:

Consideration of short-term and long-term impacts, including the time required for recovery and the anticipated effectiveness of preventive measures over time.

Risk Assessment:

Identification and assessment of risks associated with port disruptions, such as the frequency and severity of extreme weather events.

Sensitivity Analysis:

Exploration of the impact of variations in key variables, such as the severity of weather events and the effectiveness of preventive measures.

Comparison with Alternatives:

Comparison of the cost-effectiveness of preventive measures with alternative solutions, such as relocation, insurance, or other resilience strategies.

Decision Criteria:

Establishment of criteria for decision-making, such as acceptable levels of downtime, cost thresholds, and the desired level of resilience.

Scenario 2: Illegal Disposal of Wastewater Causing Environmental Damage

Define Objectives:

- Minimization/avoidance of environmental damage caused by illegal wastewater disposal.
- Installation of proper waste water management to protect the river and surrounding environment.
- Monitor the behaviour of the vessels regarding the waste management.

Identify Costs:

- Enforcement Costs: Estimation of expenses associated with monitoring and enforcing regulations against illegal waste water disposal.
- Clean-up Costs: Assessment of potential costs for cleaning and restoring the environment after illegal disposal incidents.
- Preventive Measures: Evaluation of costs for implementing measures to detect and prevent illegal disposal.

Quantify Benefits:

- Environmental Protection: Assignment of a value to the preservation of the river and surrounding ecosystem (tourism)
- Public Health: Consideration of the economic impact of avoiding health issues related to contaminated water.

Monetary Valuation:

Assignment of monetary values to costs and benefits, considering the economic value of a clean and healthy environment.

Timeframe:

Consideration of short-term and long-term impacts, including the time required for implementing preventive measures and the recovery of the environment.

Risk Assessment:

Identification and assessment the risks associated with illegal waste water disposal, including the potential extent of environmental damage and possible effects on tourism.

Sensitivity Analysis:

Exploration of the impact of variations in key variables, such as the frequency of illegal disposal incidents and the effectiveness of preventive measures.

Comparison with Alternatives:

Comparison of the cost-effectiveness of preventive measures with alternative solutions, such as increased penalties, public awareness campaigns, or technological solutions.

Decision Criteria:

Establishment of criteria for decision-making, such as acceptable levels of environmental damage, cost-effectiveness of preventive measures, and the overall impact on public health.

4.2.3 Living Lab #3 - Planning Mitigation Demonstrator App for Climate Resilient and Environmentally Sustainable Transport Infrastructure

This LL intends to build a planning proactive framework and develop an agile synchro-modal solution that connects several cities in different countries through arteries in the inland waterway system. On the one hand, the undertaken development aims to increase shipping efficiency and logistic performance. On the other hand, it is expected to strengthen the reliability and resilience of the infrastructure during a disruptive event. Therefore, it is important to create synergy between planning tools and the information on the current and future state of the network [47].

Define Objectives:

- Increasing of shipping efficiency and logistic performance.
- Strengthening the reliability and resilience of the infrastructure during disruptive events.
- Creation of synergy between planning tools and information on the current and future state of the network.

Identify Costs:

- Costs associated with developing planning tools and an agile synchro-modal solution.
- Investment in technology, infrastructure, and potentially workforce training.

Quantify Benefits:

- Improvement of shipping efficiency and logistics performance.
- Enhancement of reliability and resilience of the infrastructure during disruptive events.
- Increasing synergy between planning tools and network information.

Economic Advantages:

Potential economic advantages include cost savings through improved efficiency, increased revenue from enhanced logistics, and minimized losses during disruptive events. LL3 already provided the following information that have to be refined in more detail at a later stage of the project:

- Human casualties, vessel, cargo, salvage: €7 million
- Delay costs for vessel owners/operators: €19 million
- Rerouting & waiting costs for cargo: €5 million

Monetary Valuation:

Assignment of monetary values to costs and benefits, considering the economic impact on operational efficiency, infrastructure resilience, and overall profitability.

Timeframe:

Consideration of the time required for planning, development, and implementation of the synchro-modal solution, including short-term and long-term aspects.

Risk Assessment:

Identification of risks such as technology implementation challenges, regulatory changes, and potential environmental impacts on inland waterways.

Sensitivity Analysis:

Analysis of changes in key variables, such as technology effectiveness and market conditions that may impact the success of the synchro-modal solution.

Comparison with Alternatives:

Evaluation of the proposed synchro-modal solution against alternative approaches, such as traditional transportation methods or other technological solutions. According to the first estimations of LL3 the costs of alternative transport and transshipment amount to €24 million.

Decision Criteria:

Establishing the criteria for decision-making, considering factors such as cost-effectiveness, efficiency improvements, and the ability to withstand disruptive events.

4.2.4 Living Lab #4 – Resilience Promoting Autonomous Zero-Emissions Barges

The 4th living lab of the ReNEW project proposes to use an autonomous X-barge to demonstrate and test the improved resilience of IWT infrastructure. The main objective of the living lab is to prove the economic feasibility and competitiveness together with the climate resilient characteristics of CEMT class 4 autonomous zero-emission vessels [47].

LL4 provided already a set of costs, comparing a conventional vessel with an XBarge. The deployment of the XBarge can be seen as a strategy to deal with emissions, draught, labour shortage and economic advantages through the possibility of a 24-hour operation of the XBarge. In this context, it

is conceivable to select certain events - such as dealing with draught - in order to illustrate and compare the results between the operation of conventional ships and the XBarge.

Define Objectives:

- Evaluation of the effectiveness of XBarge as a strategy for addressing emissions, draught, and labour shortage and considering the sustainability aspect.
- Assessment of the economic advantages associated with the 24-hour operation of the XBarge.

Identify Costs:

- Initial Investment: Comparison of the costs of acquiring a conventional vessel versus an XBarge.
- Operational Costs: Evaluation of ongoing operational expenses, including fuel, maintenance, and crew wages for both options.
- Environmental Compliance Costs: Consideration of costs associated with meeting emissions standards and environmental regulations for each vessel type.

Quantify Benefits:

- Emissions Reduction: Assessment of the environmental benefits of using an XBarge in terms of reduced emissions compared to a conventional vessel.
- Draught Improvement: Quantification of the advantages of improved draught capabilities for navigating in different water depths.
- Labour Shortage Mitigation: Evaluation of the impact of the XBarge on addressing labour shortage issues, considering reduced crew requirements or increased efficiency.

Economic Advantages:

Analysis of the economic benefits derived from the 24-hour operation of the XBarge, such as increased cargo throughput and revenue.

Monetary Valuation:

Assignment of monetary values to costs and benefits, considering the economic impact on operational efficiency, compliance, and overall profitability.

Timeframe:

Consideration of short-term and long-term impacts, including the time required to balance the initial investment and the expected benefits over the operational lifespan.

Risk Assessment:

Identification and assessment of potential risks associated with each vessel type, such as technological risks, regulatory changes, or market fluctuations.

Sensitivity Analysis:

Exploration of the impact of variations in key variables, such as fuel prices, regulatory requirements, or unexpected maintenance costs.

Comparison with Alternatives:

Comparison of the cost-effectiveness and performance of the XBarge with alternative solutions, such as other vessel types or transport methods.

Decision Criteria:

Establishment of criteria for decision-making, considering factors such as emissions reduction goals, economic viability, and adaptability to changing labour dynamics.

4.3 Next Steps

The proposed scenarios outlined above, along with the corresponding approach, are currently of a more general nature and require further elaboration in consultation with the respective LL and other project partners. Since various scenarios are defined in other tasks of WP1 and WP3, it is advisable for the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to also concentrate on these identified scenarios.

In order to ensure a comprehensive and cohesive analysis, collaborative efforts and discussions with relevant LL and other project partners, will be essential. This collaborative approach aims to refine and tailor the scenarios and associated procedures to the specific needs and objectives of the individual LL. As additional scenarios may be identified during these discussions, the CBA should remain flexible and adaptable to incorporate any pertinent insights or changes that may arise throughout the consultation process.

Depending on the cost data available, a calculation model to carry out CBAs – developed by ISL for several projects - can be used for the result presentation combining the strategic with the tactical information for different scenarios. For a more flexible calculation, there are various input and selection fields for defining the criteria, such as input fields for the calculated interest rate and selection fields for choosing the frequency of the damage event. Since the calculation of costs and benefits is done on a theoretical level, no information is available when the damage event occurs. For this reason, both the costs in the event of damage and the benefits are multiplied by the possible frequency of the occurrence of damage - related to a specific time period. The calculated probabilities of occurrence are used for the calculation. The calculation model also offers the possibility of changing the downtimes of affected systems and can then show the results for the net present value, the payback period, and the internal rate of return on capital, taking into account the possible occurrence probabilities of the damage events [49].

5 Initial Resilience and Agility Strategies for IWT Infrastructures

This chapter deals with Agility and Resilience Strategies in IWT. Besides key findings based on further literature research, results of a survey conducted among the LL will be also presented. Not all LLs have responded yet, and not all events have corresponding strategies mentioned. This is partly because some events have not occurred yet or were not relevant to the respective LL. It is important to note that additional results will be provided in the next deliverable.

Agile and resilience strategies have to be distinguished. Resilience strategies prioritize withstanding and recovering from shocks, while agility strategies prioritize proactive response and adaptation. Therefore, agility strategies aim to enhance the capability to respond quickly and effectively to changing conditions. This type of strategy showcases the capacity to modify plans, actions, and operations in real-time. Agility strategies focus on proactive actions to anticipate and prepare for climate-related changes. Resilience and agility are often interconnected in practice, so a comprehensive strategy should incorporate both to effectively respond to climate change challenges.

5.1 Agility Strategies

Agility strategies aim to enhance the capability to respond quickly and effectively to changing conditions. Agility strategies focus on proactive actions to anticipate and prepare for climate-related changes.

The following strategies can be categorized as agility strategies:

Emergency Response Planning: Developing and continually updating emergency response plans for unexpected climate-related events is a crucial agility strategy [62]. LL1 mentioned this strategy in the domain of labour oriented events. LL2 mentioned this strategy in case of wildfires.

Training and Capacity Building: Training staff on climate change effects and the agile strategies in place to address them helps build the capacity to adapt quickly to changing conditions [63].

Collaboration and Information Sharing: Collaborating with meteorological agencies and other stakeholders to share information and observations related to climate change increases the ability to respond quickly.

Flexible Route Planning: Route planning systems that can be quickly adjusted based on changing weather systems, water levels and other climate-related aspects. According to LL3, the route planner that they plan to implement takes into account the water level and proposes different routes and maximum load.

Vegetation Management: Implementation of vegetation management strategies to reduce the risk of wildfires in watershed areas, as mentioned by LL2.

According to LL1, the graphs and maps provide a day-to-day monitoring of the possible drought status in the country based on 2 indices the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) which characterizes the total precipitation of the last 90 days [64].

The Standardized Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI), characterizes the water balance of the last 90 days, i.e., the difference between cumulative rainfall and evapotranspiration. Evapotranspiration is the amount of water evaporated or transpired by the soil and vegetation. Since it is difficult to measure, evapotranspiration is estimated from observations of temperature, global solar radiation, relative humidity and wind speed [64].

The tools developed in ReNEW can be deployed in any disaster or flood area in Europe after a disaster has occurred.

5.2 Resilience Strategies for Labour Oriented Events

5.2.1 Shortage of Skills and Labour

In order to successfully tackle these threats, it is necessary to develop appropriate strategies. Some of the suggestions are [65]:

1. Improving work incentives through the reform of tax and benefit systems can address labor shortages. "Tax reforms targeting low-income earners have more effect on people's labour supply than across-the-board personal income tax cuts."
2. Investing in education, skill development, training programs, and improving job matching to align with individuals' education, experience, and skills.
3. Improving working conditions to attract additional workers.

According to LL1, the existing strategy dealing with this threat is ISO standardization of the organizations, procedures and emergency plans (see emergency plans of the crisis centers).

LL1 plans to improve its existing strategies and responses to threats (taking into account the solution it offers in the ReNEW project) in the following way:

Although this specific threat is not addressed within the project for the LL2 environment, LL2 listed some strategies such as Retention Initiatives and Global Talent Pool Management. Retention Initiatives refer to implementing strategies to improve crew retention, including competitive benefits and career development programs. Global Talent Pool Management refers to developing strategies to manage crew mobility challenges during global events and pandemics.

5.3 Resilience Strategies for Crime and Cyber Attacks

5.3.1 Data Theft, Blackmail, Hybrid Attacks

Given the numerous risks associated with digitalization and data sharing, measures must be taken to avoid these risks or reduce their consequences. Security and transparency must be built into technology and processes at all levels. As a first step, the systems must be protected with strong firewall protection and strong antivirus software [66].

Regarding the data approach, only authorized organizations should be able to access them. In other words, it must be strictly determined within the organization and between cooperating organizations which data is approached by which level or by which user.

In addition, data backup and data restore are required. It is also possible to outsource the entire system. If the entire system fails or an attack occurs on the system, internal and external communications can be stopped, and a secure system can allow uninterrupted work with minimal consequences. Cybersecurity teams must be prepared to respond promptly to mitigate the negative consequences and ultimately stop the spread of ransomware or other malware in the network [66].

In addition, the IT security architecture should implement resilience strategies to limit the impact of successful attacks. Since the actors involved are in many cases in competition, a major challenge in setting up a security architecture is to ensure the confidentiality of information while maximizing transparency [66].

LL2 mentioned various strategies such as backup systems; regular cybersecurity audits (periodic assessments); and network security (firewalls and intrusion detection systems).

The CESNI/TI Working Group developed the “Best Practice Guide: Cybersecurity for Inland Ports”. The guide is divided into three parts [67]:

1. Cybersecurity threat landscape of inland navigation ports: describing the port threat landscape, including threat actors, port assets, etc.
2. Mitigating cybersecurity risks for inland navigation ports: detailing the portfolio of mitigation actions that should be taken to reduce cybersecurity risks for ports.
3. Tips for the implementation of risk mitigation measures: describing actions for the cybersecurity hygiene, i.e. tasks of institutions and individuals to preserve the health and security of systems.

5.3.2 Kidnap/Hostage and Terrorism

In a kidnap situation, if the location is known and terrestrial, security forces will surround the incident area, resulting in a barricade hostage-taking situation. These siege situations are distinct from other hostage events. Prevention during the seizure stage is challenging due to the element of surprise. Once hostages are in terrorists' hands, negotiation typically follows to secure their safe release, involving skilful techniques and potential concessions [34].

In the second situation, there are ways to minimize the risk of freight being held hostage by a driver or provider. It is necessary to choose a reliable transportation provider, make timely payments to prevent past due issues, and offer flexibility in delivery arrangements to discourage extreme measures by drivers. “Some drivers/carriers will take loads hostage because they are afraid they will be charged fines and fees that will cut into their profit” [35].

5.3.3 Outbreak of War

Numerous strategies exist that could be applied in case of war, including investment in security measures and new technology in order to protect critical infrastructure, barges, equipment, human resources, and environment, and to improve surveillance and response capabilities. Furthermore, in order to avoid enormous consequences, it is necessary to have a detailed emergency plan and cooperate with all relevant authorities at national and international levels. For example, in this way, it is possible to redirect the flow of cargo by finding alternative routes (including different transport modes). One of the examples of such strategies is the war between Russia and Ukraine. Unblocking 20 million tons of food in Odesa was one of the main goals of the EU's strategy for solidarity lanes, which include alternative logistics corridors by road, rail, and inland waterways for exporting agricultural goods (such as grain) from Ukraine. Its objective is to reroute 3 million tons of grain per month via new modal routes, including the Danube, Constanta (Romania), and Polish, Baltic and Adriatic ports [68].

5.3.4 Cargo Theft, Sabotage, Corruption, and Insider Crime

Regarding cargo theft, a rising number of providers are developing covert tracking devices within cartons or cargo, offering authorities invaluable insights into stolen cargo storage, and may help reveal typical routes to market. To address security risks, well-managed warehouse and transportation operations are crucial, involving strict security measures, training programs, and robust hiring practices for employees and third-party partners [36].

LL2 mentioned intentional or accidental blockade of locks as a possible threat. The existing strategies in case of this event are the resolution of the identified vulnerabilities, as stated by LL2. Improvement could be achieved by identifying locations in the river where passengers and cargo could shift means of transport and overcome the blockade.

5.4 Resilience Strategies for Operational Disruption Events

5.4.1 Energy Breakdown

As an existing strategy, LL1 listed Back-up battery systems and H2 fuel cells. In order to improve the existing strategies, LL1 will install extra battery packs and an Energy Management System to control the energy system supply to critical items.

Although this specific threat is not addressed within the project for LL2 environment, they mentioned several existing strategies:

- Redundant power systems: implementing redundant power systems, including backup generators and alternative energy sources, to ensure continuous operation in case of a primary energy failure.
- Regular maintenance and upgrades: conducting regular maintenance and upgrading energy infrastructure to enhance reliability and prevent system failures.

5.4.2 Technical Breakdown / Faulty of Instrumentation

Maintenance of equipment, instruments, engineering infrastructures, etc. is one of the ways to ensure smooth operation. A strategic plan for maintaining the equipment can prevent costly breakdowns and downtimes. There are different types of maintenance such as: preventive maintenance which involves regular actions like oil changes and lubrication to prevent issues. Predictive maintenance relies on real-time data to forecast when equipment might fail. Reactive maintenance is the strategy of repairing equipment after a breakdown occurs [69]. In order to achieve a successful maintenance process, skilled labour is of utmost importance, which can be achieved, among others, with various training programs.

It is also necessary to develop and implement backup systems or emergency plans in case of disruptions. The proper implementation of these plans plays a crucial role in determining the success of handling emergencies [70].

LL1 listed the following existing strategies: Spare part management, procedure for maintenance, and regular testing of the machinery and equipment. In order to improve the existing strategies, this will be part of the instructions and education of the team, and procedures of maintenance have to be done.

5.4.3 Fault or Unavailability of AIS

As for existing strategies, LL1 mentioned a backup system, track & trace with GPS and Galileo, and a camera for operational manoeuvres. In order to improve strategies, LL1 will install a backup system, and a track-and-trace device with a closed gateway to Command Center.

5.4.4 Accidents

Accidents can occur in inland navigation as a result of technical defects or, as with any human activity, due to human error [42]. In the worst case, ship accidents can result in people being injured or even killed. Shipping accidents could also lead to massive economic damage as a result of closures lasting days [43].

LL3 mentioned the TMS Waldhof incident in January 2011- compare as well Section 2.2.14. TMS Waldhof capsized and ran aground opposite the port of Loreley. During the salvaging operation, the Rhine was non-navigable for more than 32 days. The vulnerabilities that led to this accident were unstable loading of the vessel and high water levels. LL3 listed the following consequences: delays, rerouting and waiting costs of cargo, costs for alternative transport and transshipment, human casualties, and vessel and cargo casualties.

LL2 mentioned another example of an accident, i.e., communications breakdown in inland waterway traffic management. This specific threat is not addressed within the project, however, they singled out several existing strategies:

- Redundant communication systems: diverse communication channels;
- Regular maintenance and testing: scheduled inspections;
- Cybersecurity measures: advanced cybersecurity protocols;
- Emergency response plans: comprehensive emergency protocols;
- Diverse communication technologies: multi-modal communication.

LL2 mentioned also vessel grounding, as another example of an accident (although it is not addressed within the project), and the existing strategies are as follows:

- Enhanced navigation training: providing enhanced training programs for vessel operators to improve navigational skills and awareness.
- Real-time bathymetric mapping: implementing real-time bathymetric mapping technologies to provide accurate information about riverbed conditions

5.5 Illegal Wastewater Dumping

Several existing strategies are singled out by LL2:

- Stricter Enforcement and Penalties: Strengthening legal frameworks with stricter enforcement measures and higher penalties for those found guilty of illegal wastewater dumping.
- Community Awareness Programs: Conducting community awareness programs to educate the public about the consequences of illegal dumping and encourage reporting.

LL2 plans to improve the existing strategies and responses to threats in the following ways:

- Enhanced Surveillance Systems: Implementing advanced surveillance technologies to detect and monitor illegal dumping activities.
- Collaboration with Industry: Collaborating with industrial stakeholders to ensure proper disposal practices and to prevent the generation of hazardous wastewater.

5.6 Impact of Convenience Flags to Circumvent National Legislation

Although this specific threat is not addressed within the project, LL2 singled it out. As existing strategies, they mentioned:

- Enhanced Flag State Oversight: Advocating for and implementing stronger oversight measures by flag states.
- International Collaboration: Encouraging international collaboration to address the challenges posed by vessels using convenience flags.

5.7 Resilience Climate Change Adaptation Strategies

5.7.1 Introduction

For the sake of clarity, mitigation strategies and adaptation strategies against climate change have to be distinguished. On the one hand, mitigation strategies to reduce the impact and rate of climate change are widely known and mostly lead to the reduction of greenhouse gases. On the other hand, adaptation strategies should be implemented to decrease the vulnerabilities to the effects of climate change. In this deliverable, only adaptation strategies will be dealt with.

Depending on the likelihood of the climate change impact strategies can be classified into short, medium and long-term strategies [71].

Short term (0-10 years): Respond urgently to climate change impacts that are already happening, like temperature increases and increases in heavy rain.

Medium term (10-30 years): Address potential impacts based on risk assessments. Given the uncertainty of projections, decisions should be made by prioritizing. An option is to select a pessimistic projected value for high-risk impacts and an optimistic projected value for low-risk impacts.

Long term (about 30 to 100 years): Also, for long-term impacts risk assessment methods should be used. The uncertainty of projections is large on this timescale. The outcome will depend on the extent of global mitigation strategies. Consequently, flexibility is crucial to adapt strategies to the ongoing process of the implementation of strategies on a global scale.

5.7.2 Strategies

In contrast to agility strategies, the following strategies focus on the prioritization of withstanding and recovering from shocks. Consequently, these strategies can be categorized as resilience strategies.

Improvement of Wind Forecasts using Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF): Usage of the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model for accurate wind predictions. Precise and up-to-date weather information helps IWT operators decide on load, rerouting vessels or delaying trips. This is a medium-term strategy, because weather forecast improvement requires anticipation and preparedness [6].

Responsibility Allocation Considering Weather Stations in Ports: Distributing weather monitoring responsibilities among stakeholders and placing weather stations in ports for immediate data collection and coordinated responses. The allocation of responsibilities based on prevailing weather conditions signifies a prompt response to present effects, in line with short-term strategies. [72]

Regular Monitoring of Infrastructure Conditions: Monitoring infrastructure regularly is crucial for spotting potential problems before they become big issues. Regular inspections should be utilised. If possible also sensor networks, satellite imagery, and other monitoring technologies can be used for the early detection of wear and tear. The practice of regular monitoring is a proactive strategy that corresponds to current and evolving conditions, in accordance with short-term strategies. [72]

Strengthening infrastructure against flooding: Implementation of water safety strategies, like protection of the land with dike and elevation of terrain and access roads. This medium-term strategy for strengthening infrastructure involves a proactive approach that is based on risk assessments. [73]

Strengthening and Maintenance of Engineering Infrastructures: Engineering structures are essential to control the width and depth of the waterway. Well sized engineering infrastructures and rigorous maintenance should enable to direct the flow, reduce sedimentation, and erosion [74].

Regular Maintenance and Repair of Damaged Infrastructure: To ensure continuous operation, regular maintenance of the infrastructure should be scheduled. In addition, pre-emptive repairs should be carried out and emergency response teams established. Regular maintenance and overhaul are categorized as short-term strategies, serving as immediate responses to current issues. [6]

Relocation of Harbour Infrastructure: Relocating vulnerable harbour infrastructure to higher ground is a recommended long-term strategy to mitigate the impact of flooding and high waters. This strategy reduces the risk of damage to important facilities during extreme weather, keeping inland waterway transport systems working. [72]

New Design Standards for Ships: Given that IWT is already facing the consequences of low water and flooding, a short-term strategy is needed here. To protect against bigger waves and navigate shallow areas, it is crucial to establish new design standards for ships. Improved ship designs will make

vessels more stable and easier to maneuver, making IWT operations less affected by bad weather. [72]

Relocation, Redesign, and Reinforcement of Water Breaks: A short-term strategy against flooding is the protection of harbours and sea transport infrastructure against larger waves by using water breaks. [72]

Extension of Functions and Integration of River Information Services (RIS) Systems: Expanding functions and using RIS systems are vital for improved short-term flood response and navigation. RIS systems give real-time data on water levels, weather, and navigation, helping IWT operators make better decisions and improve vessel routes. [72]

Continuous and Differentiated Monitoring of rivers' water discharge regime: To fight against flooding and high waters, a short-term strategy is to implement a continuous and differentiated monitoring system for rivers' water discharge regime. [72], [71]

Model policies to promote relocation from high-risk areas: Developing strategies to incentivize the relocation of IWT infrastructure, enhancing long-term sustainability and reducing vulnerability to climate events. In this short-term strategy, there is a need for an urgent response to existing climate change impacts. [6]

Collaborate with land-use strategies, e.g. to establish buffer areas: Establish collaborative frameworks with land-use planning systems to establish buffer areas, improving protection against extreme weather events. The medium-term strategy entails evaluating risks and working collaboratively on land-use strategies to address potential impacts. [6]

Restrict new infrastructure development in high-risk areas: Implement strategies to limit new infrastructure development in high-risk areas, safeguarding vulnerable regions and preserving current infrastructure. This strategy accounts for long-term risks with significant uncertainty. The outcome depends on global mitigation strategies over 30 to 100 years, a long-term strategy. [6]

6 Building Blocks and Data Sources 2nd Release

According to the terms outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), building blocks serve as basis for the planning, operation, evaluation and impact assessment of Floating Modular Platforms, autonomous inland vessels, the digital twins as well as the benchmarking of emission-neutral solutions. The initial compilation of these building blocks is detailed in the first Deliverable D1.1.

However, recognizing the fluid nature of the project and its responsiveness to the Living Labs' (LL) requirements, the list of building blocks and data sources is scheduled for continuous updates, expansions, and specifications throughout the project's progression. Various specifications, analyses, tools, and models sourced from different projects will serve as candidates for building blocks, subject to extension, adaptation, and configuration to meet the specific functional, geographic, or process requirements of ReNEW.

In this deliverable, the decision has been made to distinguish explicitly between individual terms, as building blocks are designed to encompass both data sources and libraries. Conversely, data sources and libraries may also function independently as building blocks. Against this background, the division into corresponding subsections has been skipped.

The identification of building blocks, data sources and libraries is also required in other tasks, especially in WP3. These components are essential, such as ST3.3.2 focusing on libraries and tools for Digital Twin (DT)-enabled dynamic simulation models, with models and libraries identified and their usage described in D3.6.

Against this background and as the project transitions into a phase where practical information utilization becomes relevant, it is noteworthy that several building blocks and data sources have already been presented in the initial project phase. To facilitate the practical application of this information, the subsequent section introduces new building blocks and data sources that could offer added significance. Additionally, a comprehensive overview of the building blocks and data sources collated in D1.1 and other Work Packages is presented. This overview provides concise descriptions, accompanied by references to corresponding deliverables for more in-depth information.

6.1 Analyses, General Tools, Models, and Data Sources

Building blocks, data sources, models, and libraries based on D1.1 and other deliverables (D3.6, D3.8) are categorized in the following according to thematic focuses. The information provided in D1.1 – the previous version of this document - falling under these categories, is also assigned to these categories. New information can be found in the respective sections and is explained in more detail.

Table 2: Overview of analyses, general tools, models, and data sources

Abbreviation/Title	Details
Resilience strategies, project BREsilient	D1.1
BIVAS (Binnenvaart Analyse Systeem) - inland shipping analysis system	D1.1
Cost-Benefit-Analysis (CBA) Model (ISL)	D1.1
OpenCLSim, Open source Complex Logistics Simulation	D1.1
QGIS - desktop geographic information system (GIS)	D1.1
Ontology for Simulation (ITA, ISL – IW-NET project)	D1.1
Neo4J - graph database management system	D1.1
(Geo)data Visualization and Provision Capabilities, IW-NET project	D1.1
HALEM - Vessel route planner	D1.1
ISL Ship Engine Database	D1.1
ISL Transportation Network Database	D1.1
Vesselfinder - API and databases of real-time and historical positions	D1.1
ST4W project - IWT logistic data	D1.1
NEW - Protégé is a free, open-source ontology editor and framework for building intelligent systems	Link
NEW - OpenStreetMap (OSM) a free, open geographic database updated and maintained by a community of volunteers via open collaboration	Link
NEW - Owlready2 , a python library to work with Ontologies.	Link

6.2 Climate and Environmental Tools, Data Sources, and Models

Table 3: Overview of climate and environmental tools, data sources, and models

Abbreviation/Title	Details
Modelling cascading effects, Climate Change Impacts ASC interacting risks maps	D1.1
Copernicus - provision of climate and environmental data	D1.1
Euro-Cordex - provision of regional climate change projections	D1.1
Impactlab - Temperatures projections data; energy demand projections	D1.1
<p>NEW – GLEC, Global Logistics Emissions Council, developed the GLEC Framework, to harmonize the calculation and reporting of logistics GHG emissions across multi-modal supply chains. It is the primary industry guideline to support implementation of ISO 14083, and can be implemented by shippers, carriers and logistics service providers.</p> <p>Designed to inform business decisions that reduce emissions and track progress towards climate goals, reduce emissions. It works with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Greenhouse Gas Protocol • UN-led Global Green Freight Action Plan • CDP Reporting 	Link
NEW – EcoTransIT – tool to calculate emissions of global freight transports	Link

6.3 Weather Tools, Data Sources, and Models

Table 4: Overview of weather tools, data sources, and models

Abbreviation/Title	Details
EAC4 CAMS - global weather data, fourth generation ECMWF global reanalysis of atmospheric composition	D3.8
ECMWF - European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	D3.8
AROME - Application of Research to Operations at Mesoscale	D3.8
ARPEGE - Action de Recherché Petite Echelle Grande Echelle, tool for operational weather forecasting at Météo France	D3.8
NEW - meteo.be, weather forecasts for Belgium, observations and warnings; provision of climate projections based on climate models	Link

6.4 Hydrological Tools, Data Sources, and Models

Table 5: Overview of hydrological tools, data sources, and models

Abbreviation/Title	Details
EFAS - European Flood Awareness System	D3.8
HiPIMS, High-Performance Integrated hydrodynamic Modelling System	D1.1
LISFLOOD (Seasonal) - seasonal hydrological data and models	D3.8
LISFLOOD (Global) - global hydrological data and models	D3.8
HEC-HMS - Hydrologic Modelling System	D3.8, D1.1
HEC-RAS - hydrologic processes of flowing systems and water quality	D3.8
IRIC software platform numerical simulation of flow and morpho-dynamics in rivers	D1.1
IRIC software Nay2Dflood model calculations - flooding event analysis on rivers	D3.8
IRIC software Nays2DH model calculations - flow, erosion, and sediment transport modelling	D3.8
Kalasio, Water level forecasting - Water level forecasting using Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)	D1.1
SOBEK, modelling suite for integral water solutions	D1.1
Waterlevels / Hydrological Situation, Germany	D1.1
Waterlevels / Hydrological Situation, Europe	D1.1

6.5 Air Quality Forecast Tools, Data Sources, and Models

Table 6: Overview of air quality forecast tools, data sources, and models

Abbreviation/Title	Details
EAC4 CAMS - European Atmosphere Composition and Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	D3.8
CAMS - Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	D3.8
IQ air platform - air quality index mapping tool	D3.8

6.6 Waterways and Infrastructure Information

Table 7: Overview of waterways and infrastructure information

Abbreviation/Title	Details
River Information Services (RIS) - CESNI	D1.1
EuRIS platform (RIS-COMEX project)	D1.1
Water Framework Directive (WFD) reference spatial data sets	D1.1
Waterway information Austria: Viadonau	D1.1
Waterway information Belgium: De Vlaamse Waterweg	D1.1
Waterway information France: Voies navigables de France –VNF	D1.1
Waterway information Germany: Deutsche Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes (WSV)	D1.1
Waterway information Netherlands: Rijkswaterstaat	D1.1

6.7 Libraries

Table 8: Overview of libraries

Abbreviation/Title	Details
IWT Modelling Capabilities, IW-NET project	D1,1, D3.6
ICONET Project - New ICT infrastructure and reference architecture to support Operations in future PI Logistics NETWORKS	D3.6

7 Conclusions and Further steps

In summary, significant progress has been made in Task 1.1 concerning the design of the Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF). The identification of threats, and vulnerabilities and the formulation of strategies are fundamental steps towards improving resilience and sustainability in IWT. This also includes the development of a diverse set of KPIs and the definition of a general approach to cost-benefit analysis.

The strategies and measures developed to improve resilience and sustainability will be continuously refined as the project progresses. This will be done in close collaboration with project partners in order to tailor strategies for individual LLs based on evolving requirements.

With regard to the KPIs, the next steps include working with partners from WP1 and WP3 as well as the LLs to further classify and refine the identified KPIs. Alignment with the specifications of the Grant Agreement and a comprehensive review of the significance of each KPI are key objectives. The findings from D1.8, in which KPIs were assigned to specific resilience dimensions and phases, and specific calculation methods for the KPIs will also be incorporated into this process.

The compilation of the building blocks is essentially complete and focuses on creating a comprehensive overview. The list will be continuously reviewed and updated, with a focus on providing a general overview. A separate document is planned that will contain links to relevant deliverables in the Teams Workspace and provide project partners with easy access to detailed information.

The next steps include carrying out a cost-benefit analysis based on the scenarios developed in the ReNEW project. This includes the application of modelling approaches and the adaptation of a calculation model created by ISL for various projects. LL4 has already provided valuable cost information and serves as a starting point for this comprehensive analysis.

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